

Grant Agreement number: 101092696

Topic: HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-02

CODECO

Cognitive Decentralised
Edge Cloud Orchestration

D26: CODECO Ecosystem Community-building Report v3.0

Work package	WP7 – CODECO Ecosystem Development and Exploitation
Internal number	D7.3
Task	Task 7.1 – Toolkits Exploitation and Open-source Community-building
Due date	31.03.2026
Submission date	24.04.2026
Dissemination Type	Public
Deliverable lead and editor	ECL, David Remon
Contributing Partners	Marco Jahn (ECL), Rute C. Sofia (FOR), Fabian Wolk (UGOE), Andries Stam (ALM), Ana Solange Leal (INO), Josipa Dias (INO), Panagiotis Karamolegkos (UPRC), Rizk Allah Touma (I2CAT), Javier Serrano, Alberto del Rio (UPM), George Koukis (ATH), Juergen Gesswein (SIE), Javier Castillo (RHT), George Papathanail (ICOM)
Revision version	1.0
Reviewer 1	Rute C. Sofia, FOR
Reviewer 2	Ana Solange Leal, INO

**Funded by
the European Union**

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
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Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
**State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI**

Project Partners

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Executive Summary

D26 is the third and final deliverable of Task 7.1 (Toolkits Exploitation and Open-source Community-building) under Work Package 7 of the CODECO project. It closes the loop on a three-year open-source and community-building journey that progressed from initial awareness (D24, Year 1) through technical consolidation (D25, Year 2) to sustainability and exploitation (D26, Year 3). The reporting period covers months M25 to M39, including a three-month project extension.

The headline achievement of this final year is the formal transition of the CODECO Open-Source Toolkit into the Eclipse Foundation as the **Eclipse KuDECO** project — a vendor-neutral, Apache-2.0 licensed, professionally governed open-source project under the Eclipse Technology top-level project. This transition secures the long-term viability of the project's core technical outputs beyond the Horizon Europe funding period, providing neutral governance, professional IP management, and a sustainable infrastructure for community growth and commercial adoption.

The **CODECO Open-Source Toolkit** comprises five main components — ACM (Automated Configuration Management), PDLC (Privacy-preserving Decentralised Learning and Context-awareness), NetMA (Network Management and Adaptation), MDM (Metadata Management), and SWM (Scheduling and Workload Migration) — along with the CODEF experimentation framework, a synthetic data generator, and six use-case applications spanning smart cities, vehicular digital twins, multimedia distribution, energy management, robotics, and smart buildings. All toolkit components are licensed under Apache-2.0, ensuring business-friendly, commercially exploitable open-source software.

The **Eclipse KuDECO onboarding** followed the formal Eclipse Development Process, including a public project proposal published in July 2025, a Creation Review, and the provisioning of a permanent GitLab repository, mailing list, issue tracker, and project website. Seventeen initial committers from ten partner organisations have been named, led by FOR. A three-year operational plan (2026–2028) articulates concrete milestones for governance, technical consolidation, community growth, and financial independence.

On **IP and licence compliance**, iterative IP reviews conducted by ECL analysed 4,272 third-party dependencies across the CODECO repository using the Eclipse IP Check Tool. Of these, only seven required remedial action, all of which were resolved. Copyright header coverage across the toolkit repositories ranges from 11% to 100%, with most core components achieving above 75%. All toolkit repositories are public, carry updated README files, and follow Eclipse Foundation best practices.

Community-building in Year 3 was driven by a multi-channel strategy. The CODECO developer community grew to 69 registered members in the Eclipse Research Labs GitLab. The project maintained a strong event presence through DevConf 2025, the Red Hat Summit, ICPE/HotCloudPerf, HiPEAC 2025 and 2026, Software Crafters, and the Open-Source Community Day, among others. The flagship community event was the **CODECO Hackathon**, co-located with the IETF 123 meeting in Madrid (July 2025), attracting over 150 on-site and remote participants across 60+ projects. Two of three CODECO technical challenges were successfully completed and presented, focusing on energy-aware benchmarking and GREEN Framework validation. The **IRCEP programme** (Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme) ran 11 challenges open to SMEs, early developers, researchers, and students, supported by 33 LinkedIn posts, an informative webinar, and seven local events hosted by consortium partners.

Digital outreach reached 6,100 website visitors (17,000 views), over 8,300 Zenodo views and 8,000 downloads, 850+ YouTube views across 67 videos, and 657 LinkedIn followers. The

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project engaged across the EUCloudEdgeIoT, HiPEAC, and AIOTI ecosystems, contributing to architecture taxonomy, OSS guidelines, and standardisation activities.

In summary, D26 demonstrates that CODECO has successfully delivered on its ambition to produce "running code maintained by an active community," leaving a living legacy in Eclipse KuDECO that is positioned to drive future innovation in cognitive, decentralised edge-cloud orchestration.

Keywords: Collaboration, Communication, Community, Community building, Copyright, Developer, Development, Dissemination, Header, Intellectual Property, License, Open source, Promotion, Repository, Software, Sustainability, Toolkit.

Document Revision History:

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributors
v0.1	2026-01-20	Initial ToC	David Remon, ECL Marco Jahn, ECL
v0.2	2026-02-10	First draft	David Remon, ECL Marco Jahn, ECL
v0.3	2026-02-23	Second draft	David Remon, ECL Marco Jahn, ECL
v0.4	2026-03-06	Third draft	David Remon, ECL
v0.5	2026-03-20	Input by partners	Fabian Wolk, UGOE; Andries Stam, ALM; Josipa Dias, INO; Panagiotis Karamolegkos, UPRC; Rizk Allah Touma, I2CAT; Javier Serrano, UPM; George Koukis, ATH; Juergen Gesswein, SIE; Javier Castillo, RHT; Alberto del Río, UPM.
v0.6	2026-03-30	Input and revision by FOR	Rute C Sofia, FOR
v0.7	2026-04-01	Input and revision by INO	Ana Solange Leal, INO
v0.8	2026-04-24	Revision and Release to EC	Rute C. Sofia (FOR)

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List of Acronyms and Definitions

Acronym	Meaning
ACM	Automated Configuration Management
AGPL	Affero General Public License
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial intelligence
AIOTI	Alliance for IoT and Edge Computing Innovation
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Academia and Research
BSD	Berkeley Software Distribution
CA	Consortium Agreement
CC	Creative Commons
CI/CD	Continuous Integration and Continuous Development
CODECO	Cognitive, Decentralized Edge-Cloud Orchestration
CODEF	CODECO Experimental Framework
CR	Custom Resource
CRDs	Custom-Defined Resources
DEV	Developers
DL	Decentralized Learning
DT	Digital Twin
EC	European commission
ECA	Eclipse Contributor Agreement
EDP	Eclipse Development Process
EMO	Eclipse Management Organization
EPL	Eclipse Public License
EU	European Union
EUs	End-Users
Pub	Public in General
GA	Grant Agreement
GOV	Government, municipalities, public authorities, and policymakers
GREEN	Gauging Robust Energy Efficiency in Networks
HE	Horizon Europe
ICPE	International Conference on Performance Engineering
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Intellectual Property
IRCEP	Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme
K8s	Kubernetes
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
MDM	Metadata Management

ML	Machine Learning
Mx	Month x of the CODECO project
NetMA	Network Management and Adaptation
OCM	Open Cluster Management
OCX	Open Community Experience
OS	Open source
OSS	Open-source Software
PDLC	Privacy-preserving Decentralized Learning and Context-awareness
PV	Photovoltaic
QoE	Quality of Experience
SDO	Standardization entities and open-source communities
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
SWM	Scheduling and Workload Migration
TF	Task Force
USB	Universal Serial Bus
V2X	Vehicle-to-everything
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
WG	Working Group
Yx	Year x of the CODECO project

Acknowledgements

We would like to express our gratitude to all the partners that contributed to the development of the CODECO ecosystem community-building report. We thank all the partners responsible for CODECO modules, for their collaboration, along with partners involved in this task which do not appear as authors of this deliverable, as well as the Work Package 7 leader, INO, for their time and dedication in the development of this deliverable.

1 Introduction

This deliverable presents the CODECO open-source and community-building strategy implemented throughout the project's lifecycle.

Since its inception, the CODECO project was committed to delivering its research results as professional, sustainable, and usable open-source software (OSS) while implementing robust measures to foster a dedicated community around these open-source results.

Accordingly, this document details the activities conducted towards these goals in the context of WP7, T7.1 (based on the technical work done in WP2 and WP3) from M24 to M39. While the first year served as the initial definition and awareness phase and the second year marked the project's maturity phase, the third year focused on the exploitation of CODECO results. A primary objective of this final stage was ensuring long-term sustainability by transitioning the CODECO Open-Source Toolkit into a formal project under the Eclipse Foundation, titled Eclipse KuDECO¹.

1.1 Document Scope

This deliverable is the last one in a series of three, covering the work of *Task 7.1 - Toolkits Exploitation and Open-source Community-building*, from M25 (January 2025) to M39 (March 2026). Thus, it shows the implementation during the last year of the project lifetime of the strategy which was introduced in the Deliverable D24 [1] and developed in the Deliverable D25 [2], the Eclipse KuDECO open-source sustainable project achieved because of the CODECO project, and finally, the activities conducted during this last period. As the CODECO project has been extended for three additional months, those months are covered in this deliverable D26 as well.

Naturally, the work of T7.1 happens in close collaboration with all tasks dealing with dissemination, communication, exploitation, and ecosystem building. From the high-level perspective, these activities contribute to CODECO **Objective O5: To build a consolidated ecosystem, appealing to the different CODECO stakeholder groups.**²

1.2 Dependencies

In terms of defining the CODECO Open-source Toolkit, this deliverable is heavily dependent on the work done in WP2, mainly T2.2, T2.3, and T2.4, as these tasks laid the foundation for the CODECO architecture and the envisioned open-source ecosystem, as described in the CODECO deliverable *D10 - Technological Guidelines, Reference Architecture, and Initial Open-source Ecosystem Design v2.0* [4]. The second strong dependency is to WP3, namely T3.6, in which the actual integrated CODECO Open-source Toolkit was developed and reported in *D12 - CODECO Basic Operation and Open Toolkit v2.0* [6]. The last dependency corresponds to the work done under WP4, during the second stage of development of CODECO, T4.4, supporting tasks and extensions to the CODECO components to manage automation across federated clusters.

In terms of community-building, this deliverable is strongly related to all other tasks of WP7, which rely on a well-defined, professional CODECO Open-source Toolkit for exploitation and ecosystem development. Furthermore, it depends on WP6 because alignment is needed with the overall CODECO dissemination and communication strategy (*D21 - Dissemination, Communication, Promotion Plan* [7]).

¹ <https://projects.eclipse.org/projects/technology.kudeco>

² With a strong focus on developers

1.3 Document Structure

The deliverable is structured as follows:

- Section 2 introduces the open-source and community-building strategy for CODECO, taking into consideration the peculiarities of research projects when making it open source.
- Section 3 presents the CODECO Open-source Toolkit.
- Section 4 describes how best open-source practices are implemented to maximize the chances of creating successful open-source.
- Section 5 presents the KuDECO project, the project under the Eclipse Foundation, which will be maintained beyond the CODECO project lifetime as a sustainable open-source project.
- Section 6 reports on the community-building activities performed during M25 – M39.
- Section 7 concludes the report corresponding to the third year.
- Sections 8 and 9 are the placeholders for the community building activities developed for CODECO during the first and second years, the previous reporting periods.

2 Open-source and Community-building

The definition of open source implies that the source code is distributed under a license in which the copyright holders grant others the power to run, access, modify and re-distribute the software to anyone and for any purpose [9] [10], thus enabling the development to happen under an open, collaborative model. Throughout the years, the OSS development model has become increasingly popular around the world. Today, open-source components are the core building blocks of application software in most innovative domains, providing developers with an ever-growing selection of off-the-shelf possibilities that they can use for assembling their products faster and more efficiently [11].

Open source allows code to be used (freely), studied (in full transparency), improved and shared (collaboratively). To achieve this, there are open-source licences that comply with the open-source definition and allow the software to be freely used, modified, and shared.

Because open source is all about collaboration, the concept of communities is of major importance. Generally speaking, *“a community is a group of people united by a common identity and collective purpose who engage in activities together over time. Communities develop unique sets of shared values, principles, and norms that distinguish them from others and provide members with a sense of belonging. An open-source software community is a group of people united by the shared purpose of developing, maintaining, extending, and promoting a specific body of open-source software. These communities are often globally distributed—their members occupy different geographic regions and work across numerous industries. What unites them is their common vision for the open-source software project—as well as the spirit of camaraderie and collective identity that participating in the community affords them.”* [12].

2.1 Challenges of Open Source in Research Projects

According to a study by Ait et al. [13], *“a considerable number of projects [on GitHub] die in the first year of existence with the survival rate decreasing year after year. In fact, the probability of surviving longer than five years is less than 50%, though some types of projects have better chances of survival.”* While this study does not specifically address open-source results of research projects, the survival rate of code on GitHub resulting from research projects is not much higher than what was found in this study.

Looking at the software industry, open source is ubiquitous and has become an integral part of leading companies' business strategies and products, as corroborated by several examples [14], [15], [16], [17] and best practices [18], [19]. However, introducing an open-source strategy in a company is still not an easy task and can be a lengthy process; but once the decision is taken, measures can be implemented, the management can set structures and processes, etc.

Instead, a research project is not owned by a single entity, but consists of many different actors from industry, applied research and academia who agree to work towards a common goal (or set of goals) for a limited period. In terms of open source, the aim is to avoid the situation described by Ait et al, i.e., to avoid creating *“abandonware”* that is publicly available but has little chance of surviving beyond the three years of the research project. The nature of a research project as a collaborative endeavour for a limited period adds some complexity to achieving this goal. Different organizations from different industries, domains and backgrounds come together with diverse ideas, beliefs, and experience regarding open source. While some partners may have adopted open source in their organization, this may not be the case for others. This becomes even more important when thinking about the background and foreground of the research project. While some partners may bring an open-source background into the project, others may bring proprietary software. This has an impact on the envisioned open-source foreground to be developed during the project and poses challenges in defining which parts of the project should be released as open source and to what extent. However, if these challenges

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are properly addressed, the unique setup of a research project can be used to produce results in open source that have an impact: results that are not thrown away after a three-year project; results that are built upon, reused, extended, continued and developed after the project is over; results that have a longer-term impact on research and innovation agendas; results that can lead to new business models, start-ups and growth.

Not all these achievements can be realized in the scope of a three-year research project. But the key point is to turn the described challenges into advantages and **create a strong basis that increases the chances of reaching these goals in the long run**. To do so, a realistic yet ambitious open-source and community-building strategy must be implemented.

2.2 Open-source and Community-building Strategy

A good open-source and community-building strategy should (i) draw and keep track of the open-source landscape of the project, (ii) create an environment that allows for open collaboration right from the start, (iii) implement sufficient Intellectual Property (IP) management and (iv) lay out measures for community-building.

2.2.1 Landscaping

The open-source landscape should set the boundaries and scope of the project's open-source ambitions. It tracks partners' background and defines the output that should be released. It also identifies the existing communities associated with certain background and potential new ones. Landscaping is an ongoing activity starting from the proposal when the initial concept is drafted, continuously answering these questions: Will the project develop new tools or products? Does it aim to provide a full-fledged integrated platform? Does it aim to extend or contribute significantly to already existing tools that partners bring into the project? Or a combination of all of those?

It is important to identify and state as clearly as possible which parts of the project results will be open-source and in what form, answering the questions. This will contribute to a coherent open-source landscape for the whole project.

2.2.2 Open Collaboration Environment

As the name suggests, open-source development is meant to be done in the open. In most cases, it is not a good idea to wait until the end of the project to release code, because "*the code needs polishing before it can be shown to the public*" or "*it's not ready*", for whatever reason. Developing behind closed doors is an open-source antipathy. It will slow the project down, and the effort to "*do it later*" will continue to grow. It will cause a lot of pain.

Infrastructure (i.e., a public repo) should be set up at the start of the project, and open-source best practices should be implemented from the start. This will allow everyone to become familiar with open-source development and will encourage knowledge transfer. It is a prerequisite for reaping all the benefits of open collaboration - something that should be a pillar of any research project.

Section 4 describes the implementation of the open collaboration environment and best practices for doing proper open source.

2.2.3 Open-source Licenses and IP Management

As already mentioned, it is important to discuss open-source licences. The consortium should agree on (the types of) licences for the project results. For example, to allow commercial use of the open-source results, strong copyleft licences should not be brought into the project (at least not without prior agreement).

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Moreover, as the project runs and code is developed, it is wise to keep track of all incoming IP and licenses. The aim is to identify problems as early as possible. For example, replacing a license-incompatible library will be much easier if it is caught early, rather than later, when a lot of code already depends on it. Typically, IP and licensing are not straightforward issues and require a certain amount of training, coordination and, ideally, tool support.

Figure 1 shows the license spectrum, ordered from strong copyright (or proprietary licenses, on the right) to permissive licenses (on the left), until the *Public domain*, which corresponds to an unlicensed piece of software.

Section 4 describes how IP and license management were implemented for CODECO.

Figure 1. The OSS license spectrum.

2.2.4 OSS Community Building

When an initial open-source landscape is drawn, relevant communities can be identified. Of course, these communities are defined by open-source projects that partners bring into the project, but it is always worth thinking about other communities beyond the obvious ones. The old principle “*don’t reinvent the wheel*” also applies to community-building: Building up a new community from scratch is a long-term, time- and cost-consuming process. As with software, a lot of open-source communities exist and tapping into those is much more promising than trying to produce the next important thing, especially in the scope of a research project. Whether trying to build a new community or interacting with existing ones, we will follow the “**FREE** your community” philosophy for successful open-source community-building:

- **Feed** your community: To create and maintain a strong and sustainable relationship with a growing community, it is essential to provide it with regular information on the progress of the project while documenting the different facets of the project. At the same time, these actions allow us to build a knowledge base on the project that is accessible to all those who want to learn more.
- **Respect** your community: As soon as some code is available, it is important to share it with our communities. Even if we are not yet sure of its quality, giving access to our code to people outside the project increases our chances of getting feedback from our early adopters. “Every bug report is a love letter,” says Erich Gamma. This is true. To get that reaction, our early adopters will have to be able to (a) find our code, (b) download it, (c)

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install it, and (d) test it. And, finally, whoever encounters a problem will then have to decide to (e) contact us to report a bug, submit a request for enhancement or ask a simple question. This feedback becomes a real demonstration of their interest in our work, and we should not disappoint them.

- **Embrace** your community: The communities are not waiting for us. We may have an innovative idea, but if we do not know how to present it to these communities, if we cannot show them that we understand their needs and know how to meet them, we will miss the opportunity to attract them. That is why understanding them is essential. And the best way to achieve this level of understanding is to attend conferences, organize or participate in local events, interact with existing user groups, and, finally, meet communities you are not used to meeting.
- **Engage** your community: At some point, it is necessary to engage our communities. Remote webinars, workshops, contests, or hackathons are great ways to engage them. These bring useful feedback in terms of how the project is understood, how the platform is used, etc.

Section 6 reports on the activities towards open-source community-building for CODECO during this reporting period, while the activities during the previous reporting periods can be found in **Sections 8** and **9**.

3 CODECO OSS Assets

3.1 The CODECO OSS Toolkit

CODECO is a software-based orchestration framework, interoperable with Kubernetes (K8s), that aims to support a next generation of container orchestrators that can adapt, learn, and develop appropriate response and adaptation. The CODECO Open-Source Toolkit describes the collection of open-source components that can be used. This toolkit includes all components that deliver the CODECO platform as fully functional, exploitable open-source software: Automated Configuration Management (ACM), Privacy-preserving Decentralized Learning and Context-awareness (PDLC), Network Management and Adaptation (NetMA), Metadata Management (MDM), Scheduling and Workload Migration (SWM) (see *D12 - CODECO Basic Operation and Open Toolkit v2.0* [6]).

This section aims to provide an overview of these components from an open-source perspective. This includes a brief description of each component, its value proposition to developers, and the current state and plans for open sourcing. Figure 2 provides a high-level representation of the CODECO components.

Figure 2. High-level illustration of the CODECO framework and its main components.

Detailed in-depth specifications of each component can be found in the CODECO deliverable D12 - CODECO Basic Operation and Open Toolkit v2.0 [6], and the elaboration of the architectural design is provided in D10 - Technological Guidelines, Reference Architecture, and Initial Open-source Ecosystem Design v2.0 [4]. The next sections provide an overview of each CODECO component and the license under which they are licensed.

3.1.1 ACM: Automated Configuration Management

Summary: ACM provides methodologies and tools that support automatic configuration regarding application setup and deployment across Edge-Cloud, for single and multi-cluster environments. Aiming to provide concrete setup, configuration, and synchronization mechanisms suitable for federated cluster environments, CODECO integrates ACM, which offers automated management mechanisms to support both cluster configuration and application deployment setup, runtime workflows, and resource management (i.e., considering also non-k8s environments), and, at the same time, to assure minimum human intervention.

Value Proposition: ACM adds support for multi-clustering and resource management at the Edge, efficiently, and covers novel Cloud-to-Edge use cases explicitly.

Open Sourcing: ACM is based on the *Open Cluster Management (OCM)*³ community driven project, which is the upstream project for Red Hat Advanced Cluster Management. ACM will be licensed under Apache-2.0.

3.1.2 PDLC: Privacy-preserving Decentralized Learning and Context-awareness

Summary: PDLC is the heart of the CODECO cognitive orchestration. It is used to provide a finer-grained orchestration by developing estimations about the system stability, and providing those estimations to other components, such as SWM (for the purpose of re-scheduling). PDLC has a key role during the application run-time. Based on specific target performance profiles (e.g., resilience, greenness) provided by user DEV during the application deployment setup, PDLC i) generates combined target performance node weights based on data-compute-network; ii) generates node weight estimates based on the combined values, and resource status from cluster infrastructures. It uses this information to train decentralized learning models that aim to provide forecasting and predictions about the future behaviour of the infrastructure nodes and deployed applications. The output of PDLC is provided in the SWM K8s CR (Kubernetes Custom Resource), which can then be exploited by other CODECO components, such as SWM, to make more intelligent and insightful decisions in terms of scheduling, workload migration and resource management.

Value Proposition: Further the intelligence of cloud-edge orchestration frameworks based on cross-layer context data and decentralized intelligence that generate exploitable insights and predictions.

Open Sourcing: All developments and sub-components of PDLC are being provided as OSS. Community engagement with the component is crucial to receive feedback about the provided context information and prediction models and adapt them to best suit the needs of the community end-users. The current version of available PDLC sub-components is licensed under Apache 2.0.

3.1.3 NetMA: Network Management and Adaptation

Summary: NetMA is an advanced solution for managing and adapting networks, with the primary goal of simplifying the configuration of interconnections and enhancing the flexibility of Edge-Cloud operations. It effectively addresses the integration of internetworking control to support a wide range of network environments, including fixed, wireless, and cellular networks that will be the basis for a mobile and heterogeneous Edge-Cloud continuum, which will have to be supported by CODECO.

³ <https://open-cluster-management.io/>

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Within CODECO, NetMA plays a pivotal role in handling critical aspects such as software-defined networking capabilities, secure data exchange, predictive behaviour, and integrated network functionality exposure through standardized methods and K8s APIs.

Value Proposition: NetMA provides an improvement on the multi-domain connectivity, abstracting the local and physical location of the worker nodes by deploying an easy-to-use overlay connectivity mechanism. It also maintains a complete and updated view of the current state of the network, both underlay and overlay, enhancing the network knowledge that the network manager normally relies on (being such a view of the network state exposed and then consumed by other CODECO components).

Open Sourcing: NetMA is licensed as open-source under the Apache-2.0 license. This license allows keeping the rights of the module, but at the same time allows other potential partners to help with the maintenance and improvement of the module.

3.1.4 MDM: Metadata Management

Summary: MDM provides a common place where all metadata from systems, applications and data can be brought together on a graph. This enables sophisticated analytics to gain insights into the behaviour of complex systems, and to take action to report or correct that system behaviour. In CODECO, MDM provides an API that can be used to calculate parameters about a multi-cluster K8s system to drive intelligent application scheduling algorithms. Examples of these parameters include how 'green' the energy used for computation is, how well workloads and systems comply with predefined rules, and so on.

Metadata is provided using a JSON schema-based model that describes entities with properties and relationships between them. This metadata is provided by connectors that specialise in collecting metadata from specific systems and applications. These include K8s clusters themselves, but can be enriched with metadata about any system, provided a connector is developed for it.

The metadata model can be fully customised to the needs of a particular use case, although reuse is encouraged to facilitate the extensibility of existing applications and analysis logic.

Value Proposition: Enable mechanisms to assess how complex systems in the cloud-to-edge continuum behave by performing queries on the metadata graph. The results of the assessment can be used to drive system configuration and actuation, for example, to decide where to schedule pods across different K8s clusters. Those results may also be compared with requirements from policies defined by the end-user of those systems.

Open Sourcing: MDM is open-source, and development happens in the Eclipse GitLab repositories of the CODECO project. It leverages background assets from IBM-owned repositories that are also open-source. We expect the community to participate in the development of use cases, metadata models and corresponding connectors, with the goal of creating a rich open-source metadata collection environment for systems analysis. All components developed by IBM in the CODECO project, and particularly the MDM module, are licensed under the Apache-2.0 licence, which is considered a permissive license.

3.1.5 SWM: Scheduling and Workload Migration Summary

Summary: SWM handles the initial deployment, monitoring, and potential migration of application workloads within a single cluster and across multi-cluster environments. This means supporting the efficient (low latency, lower power consumption, data sensitivity, *Quality of Experience (QoE)*) placement of applications and their containers across the edge-cloud, derived from information provided either directly by the user or by other components, primarily PDLC (e.g., device and node availability; container centrality; network characteristics), both

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through a set of *Custom Resources (CR)*. For example, SWM handles the "best" placement (based on context-aware indicators) for the containerised components of an application to be deployed in a cluster, considering the dynamic properties of the available infrastructure, including physical/virtual machines as well as network nodes and links. Furthermore, this placement needs to be dynamically adaptable, which means achieving efficient (low latency, lower power consumption, data sensitivity, QoE) migration of containerised micro-services of an application across edge and cloud.

Value Proposition: Enhanced scheduling and dynamic migration of the workloads (pods) of distributed applications across the cloud-edge continuum, based on QoS and context criteria, completely integrated into the K8s framework.

Open Sourcing: The implementation of SWM considered background IP from Siemens AG. The current SWM solution (foreground) is fully OSS based on Apache-2.0 license.

3.2 CODEF

Summary: The CODECO experimentation framework (CODEF) is a novel microservice-based experimentation tool developed within WP5 and designed to perform CODECO validation and large-scale experimentation across the cloud-edge continuum, as a replacement for EdgeNet⁴. It flexibly covers a diverse range of resources across heterogeneous platforms and infrastructures (AWS, VirtualBox and XCP-ng, VM, physical or bare-metal), providing reproducible deployment of experiments, while covering the entire experimentation process in an automated manner, starting from node allocation from scratch (e.g., deployment and OS) to application installation and reporting of results. CODEF has also introduced a publicly accessible graphical UI that complements the existing terminal-/CLI-based code, enabling users to configure, execute and monitor multiple experiments (asynchronously) through a visual dashboard without requiring direct interaction with any command-line tooling. While remaining neither exclusively dependent upon nor confined to CODECO and its components, CODEF can deploy the complete CODECO OSS (as well as some of its standalone components) across different infrastructures to test it as a whole or its specific components, allowing the validation of CODECO in different use-cases.

Value Proposition: CODEF offers a dual-interface approach: a CLI for local and on-premises infrastructure experimentation, and a graphical UI for researchers to run experiments on crowd-sourced contributed nodes. This unified experimentation process lowers the barrier to adoption across diverse user profiles, enabling reproducible, end-to-end cross-platform benchmarking. CODEF also provides shared and federated cluster management capabilities, automating the installation of federation software such as Liqo, Karmada and OCM, while planning to enable partners and external institutions to contribute nodes in multi-tenant setups, laying the groundwork for an Experimentation and Testbed-as-a-Service (EaaS, TaaS) model. Both interfaces, along with all Ansible playbooks, experiment definitions, scripts, and documentation, are publicly accessible for community reuse and extension.

Open Sourcing: CODEF is open source and hosted in the Eclipse GitLab repository of the CODECO project. It is developed by ATH and distributed under the Apache-2.0 license.

⁴ At the time of writing of this deliverable, i.e., March 2026, EdgeNet is non-operational and its functionality is currently unavailable.

3.3 CSDG: Data Generator

Summary: Data generation, collection, and analysis are crucial for developing accurate AI/ML and *Decentralized Learning (DL)* models, enabling knowledge-driven decision-making. In the Cloud-Edge continuum, data from diverse sources and compute nodes support ML and DL models, driving forecasting, prediction, and clustering. These models support optimizing the Edge-to-Cloud ecosystem, improving energy efficiency, cluster availability, and latency. A key challenge is the limited data available before application deployment and execution. To tackle this, a synthetic data generator has been developed to simulate the output of each CODECO component, generating data for the metrics associated with the application, compute, and network. The generator simulates cross-layer data collection from CODECO components (ACM, MDM, NetMA) and outputs data in a consistent format for analysis.

The CODECO *Synthetic Data Generator (CSDG)* is an experimentation framework tool which provides CODECO components like PDLC with relevant data. It has two main sub-components:

- **The Collector:** Gathers predefined metrics (e.g., CPU, memory) directly from the monitoring engine, using Prometheus, which is ideal for cloud-edge environments and K8s-based applications.
- **The Synthesizer:** Calculates composite metrics (e.g., *MDM-freshness*, *ACM-node_failure*, *ACM-node_sec*) that can't be directly collected by Prometheus, using custom formulas.

The Data Generator simulates the CODECO components (ACM, MDM, NetMA) via CRDs and their corresponding CRs. For experimentation, the generator simulates these components to provide relevant metrics. It includes three controllers, one for each CODECO component, responsible for managing CRDs and CRs (*acm-crd.yaml*, *netma-crd.yaml*, *mdm-crd.yaml*) and deployments that track K8s nodes. The output values of the simulated ACM and NetMA components can be found by corresponding CRs using related calls to the k8s REST API. To collect the output of MDM, the simulated MDM Controller is built as a REST API Server as well, which responds with the MDM CRs, to represent the real MDM functionality.

The Data Generator can be used in order to provide data for both the Single Cluster and Federated Cluster Operations of CODECO.

Value Proposition: The synthetic data generator has been developed to simulate the outputs of each CODECO component, offering a reliable solution for system performance testing and validation. By generating data across critical metrics such as application, compute, and network, it provides a comprehensive representation of system behaviour, eliminating the need for real-world deployments. This approach enhances performance evaluation and optimization, allowing stakeholders to identify potential issues and refine system configurations in a controlled environment.

Open Sourcing: The Data Generator has been developed by UPRC and is released under the Apache-2.0 license.

3.4 Use-Cases Apps

3.4.1 P1 Smart Monitoring of the Public Infrastructure

Summary: The first use case focuses on the deployment of CODECO to optimize real-time traffic monitoring in urban environments. The use case leverages LiDAR sensors integrated with edge devices to collect and analyse 3D point cloud data, enabling the classification of vehicles and the generation of spatio-temporal traffic datasets. By integrating CODECO's task migration capabilities, workloads are dynamically redistributed across nodes within and between clusters to handle high traffic volumes effectively. This ensures uninterrupted and efficient traffic

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monitoring under various conditions, including peak traffic times. The primary objective is to demonstrate how CODECO can enhance urban traffic management by optimizing computational resources, reducing processing latency, and enabling multi-cluster coordination. Real-world applications include improving traffic flow, providing timely analytics for city planners, and enhancing public safety through better infrastructure monitoring.

Value Proposition: The value proposition of P1 lies in its ability to demonstrate CODECO's capabilities in a real-world traffic monitoring scenario. Key aspects include:

- **Dynamic Resource Allocation:** CODECO's PDLC and SWM components enable real-time task migration to balance computational loads, ensuring continuous operation even during high traffic periods.
- **Scalability:** The system's modular architecture supports seamless integration across multiple nodes and clusters, making it adaptable to a wide range of urban environments.
- **Improved Traffic Analytics:** CODECO facilitates accurate and timely traffic analysis by leveraging LiDAR data, helping city planners make informed decisions to improve urban mobility.

Open Sourcing: All the components developed for this use case, including point cloud processing tools, task migration algorithms, and deployment scripts, are open source. They are licensed under the Apache-2.0 license and accessible in the CODECO project's Eclipse GitLab repository. Additional data handling and Key Performance Indicators (KPI) gathering tools are provided for public use, ensuring transparency and collaboration opportunities.

3.4.2 P2 Vehicular Digital Twin for Safe Urban Mobility

Summary: The second use case involves the implementation of a Vehicular Digital Twin aiming to support a Vulnerable Road User (VRU) protection use case. To do so, it combines Vehicle-to-everything (V2X) technologies altogether with conventional mobile communications in order to periodically gather the position of all road actors involved in the use case. Then, the so-called Digital Twin (DT) tracks the position of all moving actors in the mobility environment to foresee possible risky situations or probable incidents. Once it is done, it issues an alert to prevent something like this from happening. The modules involved in the use case implement a myriad of features, from the capability of processing V2X messages, going through the compression of all the geopositioned measurements in short messages, to the constant loop, which checks for future situations, along with the processing of all gathered information.

Value Proposition: This use case offers the infrastructure deployment of V2X services across an edge-cloud continuum environment, the capability of decentralizing the processing of geopositioned data across multiple nodes, together with the periodic handling of GPS measurements gathered from a mobility scenario to prevent potential incidents.

Open Sourcing: All the functional modules implemented for the current use case are open source, with the peculiarity that some of them import the i2CAT ETSI C-ITS protocol stack implementation, called V2X Flexstack, which is also open source, but licensed under a more restrictive Affero General Public License (AGPL). Apart from that, all the features will be available for anyone to use, from the data handling to the KPI gathering solution.

3.4.3 P3 MDS across Decentralised Edge-Cloud

Summary: The P3 use case is oriented to **enhance communications in multimedia content distribution services**. This is achieved through the deployment of specific monitoring tools for this type of service, such as user IDs or geographic areas, as well as the collection and prediction of network and computational capacities by the CODECO framework. This use case seeks the integration of the deployed software's own metrics, such as geographic areas or user requests, with CODECO's own information, extracted by ACM and NetMA. In addition, the use

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of prediction and scheduling tools such as PDLC and SWM will allow the number of caches located on the edge to be optimized, saving both computational and network resources, which can have a great impact on a real network, as it is one of the main consumptions by users on a daily basis.

Value Proposition: The added value that the MDS use case brings to CODECO is to demonstrate how this framework can simplify and optimize a traffic management system as widespread in today's networks as an MDS. Among the main points to demonstrate, we can list:

- **Use of open-source tools for the integration of metrics.** Both the code developed in CODECO, and the one used in the use case are based on open-source deployments, the metrics being extracted with protocols such as ALTO or Netperf and with APIs such as MEC. This integration of multiple metrics from open tools and protocols is an incentive for Open-Source collaboration.
- **Modular architecture for scalability.** One of the foundations of CODECO is the use of individual components that reduce dependencies between them, giving greater flexibility to the environment. This flexibility helps the use case to be deployed in different environments with different characteristics, reducing scalability complications.
- **Optimization of the use of network and computing resources.** From AI-based predictions, CODECO manages instantiated resources to optimize communications and resource usage, making the system more efficient and sustainable.

Open Sourcing: All the data created, as well as the code instantiated within the use case, is open source, licensed under the Apache-2.0 license and available in the Eclipse GitLab repository of the CODECO project.

3.4.4 P4 Demand Side Management in Decentralized Grids

Summary: The P4 use case focuses on applying CODECO to optimize **demand-side energy management in decentralized grids**, enhancing energy efficiency and sustainability. CODECO supports the deployment and orchestration of energy applications across edge and cloud environments, using a modular and scalable architecture. The system leverages Internet of Things (IoT) sensors to monitor energy consumption, photovoltaic (PV) generation, and battery levels in real time. Predictive analytics and dynamic task scheduling optimize energy usage, reduce carbon emissions, and balance grid loads effectively. Applications include energy monitoring, forecasting, and dynamic task orchestration, all integrated into the CODECO framework. Key components such as ACM, MDM, PDLC, SWM, and NetMA ensure efficient deployment, data integration, and fault tolerance. The use case demonstrates CODECO's ability to optimize energy performance across multiple nodes, buildings, and campuses, aligning with global sustainability goals.

Value Proposition: The value proposition of the P4 energy use case lies in its capability to demonstrate CODECO's integration into real-world energy management, fostering scalability, efficiency, and innovation. Key value points include:

1. **Open-Source Accessibility:** The energy management applications and predictive models are open-sourced, fostering reproducibility and collaboration. Docker images for energy monitoring and forecasting are accessible via CODECO repositories, encouraging adoption and integration into similar energy systems.
2. **Modular Architecture for Scalability:** The system's modular design, with distinct CODECO components (e.g., ACM, MDM, PDLC), enables flexible and scalable deployment across edge and cloud environments. This architecture is adaptable to various energy assets, such as PV systems and battery storage.

Open Sourcing: All the data and most of the functional modules implemented for the current use case are open source. Code is available on the CODECO Eclipse GitLab.

3.4.5 P5 Wireless AGV control for flexible factories

Summary: The P5 use case applied the CODECO framework to *Automated Mobile Robots (AMR)*, following the initial concept based on *Automated Guided Vehicle (AGV)* fleets operating in Manufacturing environments. The use-case aims to improve fleet resilience and energy efficiency through better distribution of application workloads across the available infrastructure. CODECO assisted in the deployment and dynamic rescheduling of robotics applications in response to connectivity disruptions, node failures, or resource constraints, with the goal of reducing energy expenditure and improving task completion times.

The application workload was developed and validated in the fortiss IIoT Lab, using a physical testbed comprising a K8s master node (Lenovo ThinkPad X280), Raspberry Pi 4 worker nodes, and TurtleBot3 Burger AMRs. The AMRs were configured to perform three distinct logistics tasks, each representing a common material handling scenario within a factory warehouse: collection from a pick-up station and return to a docking station, collection from an alternative station, and a multi-stop transfer between stations.

The autonomous navigation application developed for this pilot comprises three micro-services built on ROS2: **Bringup** initialises the AGV's core systems — including communication interfaces, ROS2 nodes, sensors, and actuators — ensuring hardware is operational and enabling remote control and visualisation via a controller node. **SLAM** (Simultaneous Localisation and Mapping) enables autonomous driving by mapping the surrounding environment using Google Cartographer. As TurtleBot3 AGVs lack the onboard processing capacity for computationally intensive SLAM tasks, these are offloaded to a remote PC operating within the same subnet. AGVs publish sensor data — including laser scans and odometry readings — via ROS2 topics, transmitted to the PC using Data Distribution Service (DDS). The SLAM Docker image is openly available on the CODECO DockerHub. **Navigation** uses Nav2 for autonomous movement planning and execution. The controller node subscribes to AGV data, processes it for mapping purposes, and runs Nav2 for path planning. Key nodes — including `amcl`, `planner_server`, and `controller_server` — ensure efficient navigation, with AGVs following predefined waypoints via a Waypoint Follower.

Value Proposition: The P5 robotics application demonstrated the feasibility of testing and validating CODECO in mobile automated robot environments, using the TurtleBot3 ROS2 platform as the basis for a proof-of-concept built around modular, scalable micro-services. Its principal value contributions are as follows.

Open-source accessibility. The three micro-services — Bringup, SLAM, and Navigation — together with their respective Docker images (supporting both ARM architecture on TurtleBot controllers and x86 on PC), are openly available via the CODECO Eclipse GitLab⁵ and CODECO DockerHub, fostering reproducibility, collaboration, and integration with third-party systems.

Modular architecture for scalability. The use of distinct, independently deployable micro-services orchestrated through K8s makes the system flexible and adaptable across different robotic platforms and operational environments. The repository is structured to support Docker-based deployment, CODECO-based scheduling and workload placement, KinD-based evaluation for stateful SLAM migration testing, and a full demo workflow with monitoring and dashboard control.

Robust autonomy at the far Edge. The integration of advanced navigation algorithms (Nav2) and waypoint-based task execution within a TurtleBot-based application provides a representative testbed for validating CODECO's orchestration capabilities in far-edge environments characterised by constrained and intermittent wireless connectivity.

⁵ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/use-cases/p5-amr-manufacturing>

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Persistent data accessibility and resilience. The use of K8s PV/PVC ensures that critical operational data — such as environment maps constructed during SLAM — remains available across node transitions, enabling seamless workload handover without data loss. The ability to cordon and drain nodes to trigger migration was demonstrated both in a virtual KinD cluster and on the physical TurtleBot3 testbed, validating the approach under realistic conditions.

Open Sourcing: Code and documentation are copyright 2023-2026 fortiss GmbH, released under an Apache 2.0 licence. Documentation is licensed under Creative Commons (CC). All code is available on the CODECO Eclipse GitLab project for P5¹.

3.4.6 P6 Smart Buildings

Summary: In Use Case P6, the focus lies on applying CODECO in the deployment and orchestration of edge applications in smart offices. The basic technology applied in the use case is the Crownstone technology developed by ALM. Miniaturized hardware devices called Crownstone nodes are built into the power outlets of a building. They can switch on and off devices connected to their power outlet, they can measure the power consumption of those devices, form a mesh network with other Crownstone nodes to communicate, they can be attached to external Bluetooth-enabled sensors and actuators, and, finally, they are capable of running small programs on their processor, called micro-apps. Furthermore, the network of Crownstone nodes enables indoor localisation of people and devices; together with Crownstone hubs (Raspberry Pi devices extended with special Universal Serial Bus (USB) Crownstone nodes), they form an edge network where applications can be deployed. Finally, a Crownstone cloud component enables the buildup of history around the usage of the office by people and the power consumption of devices in the office.

Value Proposition: CODECO is used in this use case to ease the deployment and reconfiguration of applications in the Crownstone network. In particular, the focus is on the following aspects:

- **Extreme far edge involvement:** Automated deployment enabled via K8s, even up to the level of the individual Crownstone nodes, which are involved by means of proxy worker nodes called Virtual Kubelet.
- **Topology-based (re)deployment:** The Crownstone network is capable of informing CODECO about changes in its hardware topology, e.g. the addition or removal of a Crownstone node in the network, based on which CODECO can decide to alter the application configuration in the network.
- **Occupancy-based (re)deployment:** The indoor localisation and occupancy information can (either directly or indirectly) be utilized by CODECO for maintaining the desired state of deployment based on the presence of people or occupancy density levels.

Open Sourcing: The Crownstone node firmware is completely open source and currently published on GitHub⁶. Software development done for the P6 use case is open source as well and available in the CODECO Eclipse Gitlab⁷.

⁶ <https://github.com/crownstone>

⁷ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/use-cases/p6-crownstonesmartbuildings>

4 Implementing Open Collaboration Best Practices

During the first year of the project's life, the partners in charge of development designed the CODECO architecture and implemented an initial version of the CODECO Open-source Toolkit, and consequently, the work around this code was devoted to setting up the environment and paving the ground for open collaboration. During the second year, the CODECO Open-source Toolkit reached its maturity phase, the software development work in CODECO continued as expected, and the Research Labs repository took good shape, allowing ECL partner to help with the IP work around the code and the repository, following the open-source good practices. During the last year of the project lifetime, the CODECO Research Labs repository continued evolving, got ready to become an open-source project under the Eclipse Foundation and finally moved there. The work on IP done by the CODECO partners, led by ECL, facilitated migration to a technology Eclipse project under the Foundation.

The application of the open-source best practices has been translated into statements which have been put into practice in CODECO, among which the following ones can be highlighted:

- All the CODECO repositories in Research Labs should be public. No work in private is allowed in the public repository, and all the issues and discussions should be public.
- All the CODECO repositories should have a *Readme* file, facilitating the engagement and adoption of the CODECO code by external developers.
- All the CODECO source code files (when the programming language allows it) will have a copyright header, following the structure explained in Section 4.2.1.
- All the CODECO components will use open-source libraries, and the 3rd party library conflicts or issues will be solved by the developers.

The first three points are covered under Section 4.2.2, as they correspond strictly to *best practices*, while the last one is not rigorously a *best practice* but corresponds to an *IP potential issue*, and therefore is covered in Section 4.3.2.

4.1 Open Collaboration – Eclipse Research Labs

Open (and transparent) collaboration is one of the pillars of open source. Collaborative development in the CODECO public repository started at an early stage of the project. The CODECO developers joined forces from the beginning, and by the end of the first year, 35 developers had joined the members in the CODECO Research Labs in Gitlab. It continued to grow up to 51 developers at the end of year 2, achieving a **total of 69 developers** at the end of the third year of all of whom are or were consortium members. With IRCEP and the IETF Hackathon, an additional 20 developers were attracted.

Attracting external contributors beyond the consortium remains the primary challenge and a core objective of Eclipse KuDECO's first operational year. This development materialised in an initial snapshot of the CODECO open-source toolkit released in M10 (*D11 - CODECO Basic Operation and Open Toolkit v1.0* [5]) and a stable version of the same released in M18 (*D12 - CODECO Basic Operation and Open Toolkit v2.0* [6]).

4.1.1 Research Labs

Eclipse Research Labs is a combination of infrastructure (GitLab), processes and training to implement open-source best practices right from the start and increase the chances of delivering high-quality, professional open-source results (see also the deliverable *D10 – CODECO Technological Guidelines, Reference Architecture, and Open-source Ecosystem Design v2.0* [4]).

Eclipse Research Labs aims to gradually and continuously preparing research results to become proper open-source projects during the research project lifetime.

In the Research Labs, as in any other GitLab project, two types of entities can be found:

- A subgroup, which allows managing the members who have access to the content inside but does not host code.
- A project, which is the equivalent of a sub-repository, where the code is hosted. A project under another higher-level project may be called a subproject.

Specifically, the CODECO Research Labs repository is structured following the components of the Open-source Toolkit (see Figure 3), along with some other specific subprojects:

- One subgroup per CODECO component (ACM, MDM, NetMA, PDLC and SWM).
- A subgroup named “*Experimentation Framework and Demonstrations*”, which hosts the CODECO datasets, a data generator to allow running CODECO components and integration and experimentation tools (see Figure 4).
- Another subgroup containing a few Datasets, mainly corresponding to the pilots.
- A subgroup devoted to the CODECO Use Cases, containing code specific to each Pilot (see Figure 5).
- One more subgroup, “*Hackathon*”, containing the code corresponding to the three challenges created for the CODECO hackathon, as depicted in Figure 6. The CODECO hackathon is further detailed in Section 6.3.1.1.
- Another subgroup, “*IRCEP Challenges*”, hosts the repositories and code to support the IRCEP initiative and the local challenges organized. The IRCEP Program is explained in detail in its corresponding deliverable *D28 CODECO Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme* [8].
- A last sub-project called “CODECO-integration”, which contains scripts to test the CODECO components along with integration scripts and the instructions to deploy the CODECO framework on your machine and in a Docker container.

Eclipse Research Labs / CODECO Project

CODECO Project

Cognitive, cross-layer and highly adaptive Edge-Cloud management framework

Recent activity **Last 30 days** Merge requests created **11** Issues created **15** Members added **2**

Subgroups and projects Shared projects Shared groups Inactive

Search (3 character minimum) [Q] Name [v] [↑]

>	D	Datasets	Owner	0	8	1	:
>	E	Experimentation Framework and Demonstrations	Owner	3	1	1	:
>	H	Hackathon	Owner	3	0	5	:
>	I	IRCEP Challenges	Owner	11	1	2	:
>	M	Metadata Manager - MDM	Owner	0	3	1	:
>	N	Network Management and Adaptation - NetMA	Owner	0	6	1	:
>	P	Privacy-preserving Decentralised Learning and Context-awareness - PDLC	Owner	1	4	1	:
>	S	Scheduling and Workload Migration - SWM	Owner	0	2	3	:
>	U	Use-Cases		2	5	3	:
	A	Automated Configuration Management - ACM		★ 5			3 hours ago
	C	CODECO-integration		★ 0			3 days ago

Figure 3. The CODECO Research Labs GitLab.

Eclipse Research Labs / CODECO Project / Experimentation Framework and Demonstrations

E Experimentation Framework and Demonstrations

Subgroups and projects Shared projects Shared groups Inactive

Search (3 character minimum) [Q] Name [v] [↑]

	B	Benchmark Tools	Owner	0	0	1	:
∨	D	Data Generators and Datasets	Owner	0	1	1	:
	S	Synthetic Data Generator		★ 1			1 month ago
∨	E	Experimentation Projects		0	4	1	:
	G	gitlab-profile		★ 0			3 months ago
	O	OnlineRL Paper		★ 0			3 months ago
	P	PDLC Influx Code		★ 0			3 months ago
	R	Recommendation Collector		★ 0			7 months ago
	E	Experimentation Framework		★ 0			2 months ago

Figure 4. The Experimentation Framework and Demonstrations sub-group.

Eclipse Research Labs / CODECO Project / Use-Cases

U Use-Cases

Subgroups and projects Shared projects Inactive

Search (3 character minimum) [Q] Name [v] [↑]

>	P	P1-SmartCity	0	1	1
>	P	P2 - VehicularDT	1	1	3
	P	P3 - MEC Enablement	0		6 days ago
	P	P4-DEM-Energy	0		6 days ago
	P	P5-AMR-Manufacturing	0		5 days ago
	P	P6-CrownstoneSmartBuildings	0		4 days ago

Figure 5. Use-Cases sub-group.

Eclipse Research Labs / CODECO Project / Hackathon

H Hackathon

Subgroups and projects Shared projects Shared groups Inactive

Search (3 character minimum) [Q] Name [v] [↑]

∨	C	Challenge 1 - GREEN	Owner	0	2	1	
	D	Documentation		0			3 weeks ago
	Y	YANG Exporters		0			7 months ago
∨	C	Challenge 2 - CATS	Owner	0	1	2	
	C	CODECO CATS		0			3 weeks ago
∨	C	Challenge 3 - BMWG	Owner	0	5	1	
	C	CODEF		0			7 months ago
	D	Documentation		0			7 months ago
	E	Experiment-examples		0			7 months ago
	G	gitlab-profile		0			7 months ago
	V	vm-template-tools		0			7 months ago

Figure 6. CODECO Hackathon sub-group.

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Eclipse Research Labs not only hosts the CODECO open-source repository but allows the developer to have access to a *wiki*⁸ page which details the open-source good practices recommended to be followed in software development.

Lastly, *Continuous Integration and Continuous Development (CI/CD)* procedures are implemented under the scope of WP3. Every time there is a relevant code update, through a merge request in any of the CODECO sub-repositories, the pipelines are executed in Runners⁹, building a new image of the CODECO Toolkit. A general look at the pipelines corresponding to the CODECO project can be seen in Figure 7.

The screenshot shows the GitLab Runners interface for the CODECO project. It displays three runners with the following details:

Runner ID	Configuration	Owner	Status	Version	Last Contact	Created By	Created At
#2106 (-vzG2Vsr)	icom-runner-codeco	P3 - MEC Enablement	Online	17.5.3	17 minutes ago	Konstantinos Karageorgos	4 weeks ago
#2103 (D8Rbt2-D)	rhat-runner	Automated Configuration Management - ACM	Online	-	40 minutes ago	Dean Kelly	1 month ago
#1782 (zyhyPixB)	sie-acc-gw	Workload Placement Solver	Online	17.0.0	5 minutes ago	Jürgen Geßwein	6 months ago

Figure 7. Pipelines in GitLab Runners corresponding to the CODECO project.

4.1.2 Development Process

In order to implement *open collaboration* as an open-source best practice, the CODECO developers have used an AGILE methodology, working with issues or tickets, boards and continuous follow-up. This methodology allows not only tracking of the progress and assignment of responsibilities but also enables direct and quick communication among partners on specific

8 <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/groups/eclipse-research-labs/-/wikis/home>

9 <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/groups/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/-/runners>

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matters or issues. The next two figures show snapshots of the CODECO issue list (Figure 8) and issue board (Figure 9) at the time of writing this deliverable.

The screenshot shows the 'Issues' page for the 'CODECO Project' in the Eclipse Research Labs. It features a navigation bar with 'Open 49', 'Closed 242', and 'All 291' filters, along with 'Bulk edit' and 'Select project to create issue' buttons. A search bar and sorting options are also present. The main content area lists several open issues, each with a title, a brief description, a list of labels, and an update timestamp.

Issue Title	Labels	Updated
Unwanted pod-scheduling behaviour on vnode	ALM, Pilot Issue, Pilot Related, T5.3	updated 7 months ago
CODECO FC - Error Netma collection on pdlc-dp	FC Related	updated 3 days ago
swm controller does not redeploy deleted workload pods and removes everything	Bug	updated 6 hours ago
swm controller crashes when pod has ExitCode:1 and does not redeploy	Bug, Important	updated 6 hours ago
CODECO workload does not have label to link a service	Bug, Low Priority	updated 4 days ago
P5 : ACM does not propagate taint / cordon status to the Solver	ALM, FOR, May need Workaround, Not a Bug, Pilot Issue, Pilot Related, T5.3	updated 6 days ago
Surface overlay misconfiguration in CRD status for easier debugging	Low Priority	updated 6 days ago
global: metrics standarization documentation		updated 5 days ago
documentation: acm documentation inconsistent with codeco documentation		
post deploy script: installing flannel before any other requisites		
PDLC not generating runtime recommendations for a 3-node Kind cluster		updated 3 days ago
Error Handling and Poll Logic needs Enchantment	Enhancement, Help Wanted, Out of Scope	updated 1 month ago

Figure 8. Most recent issues currently open in CODECO Research Labs.

Figure 9. Current status of the issue board in CODECO Research Labs.

These issues, where the discussions and work take place, are public and are available in the CODECO Research Labs Issue List¹⁰ and Issue Board¹¹, at the project level and a CODECO component level as well. Whoever visits the project and reads the issues will have an idea of the work put behind this code and project, generating trust while feeding and respecting our community (see section 2.2.4).

10 <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/groups/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/-/issues>

11 <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/groups/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/-/boards>

4.2 Copyright Headers and Repository Best Practices

4.2.1 Copyright Headers

According to the open-source best practices, appropriate **copyright headers** should be added to all relevant files in the repositories. Copyright headers for CODECO are intended to follow the Eclipse Foundation recommendations as described in the Eclipse Foundation Project Handbook¹² and depicted in Figure 10. The headers consider the following fields:

- 1) Name of the initial copyright owner (this must be a legal entity); other organisations that have contributed are either listed individually or grouped by appending "and others". The year is expressed either as a single year or a range spanning the year of the initial creation and that of the most recent change.
- 2) Declared project licenses described in human readable form.
- 3) Declared project licenses are indicated using SPDX codes and expressions.
- 4) The names of the contributors and the nature of their contribution (this section is optional and may be excluded).

```

/*****
 * Copyright (c) {year} {owner}[ and others] ❶
 *
 * This program and the accompanying materials are made available under the ❷
 * terms of the Eclipse Public License 2.0 which is available at
 * http://www.eclipse.org/legal/epl-2.0.
 *
 * SPDX-License-Identifier: EPL-2.0 ❸
 *
 * Contributors: ❹
 *   {name} - initial API and implementation
 *****/

```

Figure 10. Copyright header in the CODECO OSS code.

During the previous reporting period, ECL developed two tools which measured the usage of Copyright headers in the source code files present in the CODECO repository and added a Copyright header when it was missing. These two tools, *Add License*¹³ and *BP Check*¹⁴, have been used during the last year for the IP checks and the application of the open-source best practices to the code. Both tools are open source and are available in the Research Repository¹⁵ under the Eclipse Research Labs.

4.2.2 Repository Best Practices Implementation

During the third year, ECL has continued to iteratively apply the tools enabling the implementation of the best practices in the CODECO Research Labs and, as a result, the condition of the repository from an open-source perspective has continued to be high-grade. As it will be described in **Section 5**, this has accelerated the transition to the Eclipse project, since the IP Review of the initial Eclipse KuDECO code will be smoother. This section shows the current status of this project regarding the three points mentioned in **Section 4**: repository visibility, availability of *README* files and utilisation of copyright headers.

12 <https://www.eclipse.org/projects/handbook/#ip-copyright-headers>

13 <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/research-eclipse/add-license>

14 <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/research-eclipse/bp-check>

15 <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/research-eclipse>

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The CODECO Research Labs repository has increased the hosted code along with the project progress. Initially composed of the CODECO components, it has then hosted the project initiatives which required a repository, as mentioned in *Section 4.1.1 Research Labs*, such as the Use Cases, the IRCEP Challenges and the Hackathon, the Datasets, etc.

Firstly, all the sub-repositories under the CODECO Research Labs are set as public, being available to external developers, and have updated the *README* file. Secondly, regarding copyright headers, most of the repositories are using copyright headers in their source code files, therefore identifying the entity which owns the copyright for the file.

Focusing on the CODECO Toolkit and the CODECO components, which transition and become the formal Eclipse KuDECO, Table 1 shows the CODECO Toolkit sub-repositories and their visibility, license and presence of updated Readme file. Table 2 shows the copyright owner, declared in the copyright headers, and the percentage of source code files including a copyright header for each corresponding CODECO sub-repository.

Table 1. CODECO Toolkit repositories' visibility, license used and presence of Readme file.

CODECO Sub-project	Visibility	License	Readme file
acm	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
experimentation-framework-and-demonstrations/data-generators-and-datasets/synthetic-data-generator	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
experimentation-framework-and-demonstrations/experimentation-framework	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
metadata-manager-mdm/connectors	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
metadata-manager-mdm/graphdb	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
metadata-manager-mdm/mdm-api	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
network-management-and-adaptation-netma/network-exposure	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
network-management-and-adaptation-netma/network-state-management	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
network-management-and-adaptation-netma/network-state-management/-/tree/main/netma-nsm-mon	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
network-management-and-adaptation-netma/network-state-management/-/tree/main/netma-nsm-npp	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
network-management-and-adaptation-netma/secure-connectivity	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/pdlc-ca	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/pdlc-deployment	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/mlops	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md

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CODECO Sub-project	Visibility	License	Readme file
privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-gnns	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-rl	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/pdlc-dp	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
scheduling-and-workload-migration-swm/qos-scheduler	Public	Apache-2.0 CC-BY-SA-4.0	README.md
scheduling-and-workload-migration-swm/workload-placement-solver	Public	Apache-2.0 CC-BY-SA-4.0	README.md

Table 2. Copyright owners for the CODECO Toolkit repositories and % of files including headers.

CODECO Subproject	% copyright headers	Copyright Owners
acm	79%	Red Hat Inc.
experimentation-framework-and-demonstrations/data-generators-and-datasets/synthetic-data-generator	88%	University of Piraeus Research Centre Telefónica Innovación Digital fortiss GmbH
experimentation-framework-and-demonstrations/experimentation-framework	60%	Athena RC Red Hat Inc. Others
metadata-manager-mdm/connectors	75%	IBM Corp.
metadata-manager-mdm/graphdb	100%	IBM Corp.
metadata-manager-mdm/mdm-api	48%	IBM Corp.
network-management-and-adaptation-netma/network-exposure	39%	Telefónica Innovación Digital Others
network-management-and-adaptation-netma/network-state-management	44%	Others
network-management-and-adaptation-netma/nemesys-fc	11%	Telefónica Innovación Digital
network-management-and-adaptation-netma/network-state-management/-/tree/main/netma-nsm-mon	41%	fortiss GmbH
network-management-and-adaptation-netma/network-state-management/-/tree/main/netma-nsm-npp	41%	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
network-management-and-adaptation-netma/secure-connectivity	13%	Others
privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/pdlc-ca	92%	fortiss GmbH

CODECO Subproject	% copyright headers	Copyright Owners
privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/pdlc-deployment	100%	University of Piraeus Research Centre
privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/mlops	100%	Intracom Telecom
privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-gnns	37%	Intracom Telecom
privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-rl	94%	Siemens AG I2CAT Foundation
privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/pdlc-dp	94%	University of Piraeus Research Centre I2CAT Foundation Siemens AG
scheduling-and-workload-migration-swm/qos-scheduler	98%	UC3M Siemens AG Others
scheduling-and-workload-migration-swm/workload-placement-solver	77%	Siemens AG

Several sub-repositories exhibit copyright header coverage below 50%, e.g., `netma/nemesys-fc` (11%), `netma/secure-connectivity` (13%), `netma/network-exposure` (39%), and `mdm/mdm-api` (48%). In each case, the lower coverage reflects a combination of configuration and infrastructure files for which headers are not required by Eclipse Foundation guidelines, and a subset of source files where header addition was still in progress at the time of this report. Specifically, `nemesys-fc` and `secure-connectivity` contain a high proportion of YAML and shell configuration files which are excluded from the header requirement; the remaining uncovered source files have been flagged in the Research Labs issue tracker and are expected to be addressed as part of the Eclipse KuDECO IP review conducted by the EMO. The CODECO component leaders for NetMA and MDM have been informed and have committed to resolving the outstanding files prior to the first KuDECO release.

Finally, we would like to highlight that the CODECO code base continues to evolve, as **evidenced by the transition of the CODECO Open-Source Toolkit into the formal Eclipse KuDECO project**. Consequently, the application of the open-source best practices will continue to be monitored within the final hosting environment for the Eclipse KuDECO code on GitLab, overseen by the Eclipse Management Organization (EMO)¹⁶.

4.3 OSS Licenses and IP Validation

4.3.1 OSS Licenses in CODECO

As discussed in **Section 2**, IP and license management are an important part of open-source software development. Two steps need to be considered:

- The license(s) under which the CODECO open-source components are made available. This license regulates the way other developers use the CODECO Toolkit.
- Compatibility with the licenses of third-party libraries used by CODECO components. These licenses regulate the use of other software in CODECO.

¹⁶ <https://www.eclipse.org/projects/handbook/#roles-emo>

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The initial basic agreement for CODECO open source is that it would be licensed under a permissive or weak copyleft license. By default, this includes Apache-2.0, MIT, Berkeley Software Distribution (BSD)-3-Clause, and EPL-2.0. The use of other licenses was not initially recommended but would be decided based on prior discussion among the consortium members. By the time the first version of the CODECO Toolkit was released, in M18, it was agreed by the CODECO component leaders and developers that, in general, all the CODECO components would be licensed under Apache-2.0. It was presented at a CODECO General Assembly as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11. All the CODECO components and sub-components licensed under Apache-2.0.

The utilisation of one unique license for the whole CODECO Toolkit is not a coincidence. Licensing a project under only one license shows consistency and is an open-source good practice. Moreover, if that open-source license is a well-known business-friendly license, such as Apache-2.0, external developers will not be concerned about the use of the code in this repository, but will feel comfortable, with the main goal of fostering adoption.

The CODECO Research Labs repository, like every other software repository, includes the source code files and the corresponding documentation, which has been partially licensed under Creative Commons 4.0, CC-BY-SA-4.0.

On the other hand, in the CODECO Research Labs, the five CODECO components can be found, which represent the core of the CODECO Toolkit, along with other repositories, such as the six use cases. The CODECO use cases are not considered part of the CODECO Open-source Toolkit *per se*. They consume it and represent six applications of the CODECO Toolkit.

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Therefore, the code in those repositories may be licensed under another open-source license, different from Apache-2.0.

4.3.2 IP Validation

Third-party license compliance is checked semi-automatically regularly, using an appropriate tool developed by the Eclipse Foundation. At the beginning of the project, the *Eclipse Dash License Tool*¹⁷ (short: Dash License) was being used. Dash License identifies the licenses of content and is intended primarily for use by Eclipse committers to vet third-party content used by their Eclipse open-source project. During the second year of CODECO, the Eclipse Foundation developed a new tool, the *IP Check Tool*¹⁸. It offers the same functionalities as the original *Dash License*, improving usability and scalability, while adding some extra features.

None of these two tools identifies dependencies (at least not in general). Rather, the value they provide starts once the list of dependencies is identified by build tools. The tools are as good as the input provided, and it is up to the committer to ensure that the input, the list of dependencies, is correct. That means, dependencies which are not automatically discovered by build tools must be vetted manually.

For any license-incompatible library found, the developer of the respective CODECO component is asked to replace it, i.e., look for a library providing similar functionality under a compatible license.

ECL has iteratively applied the *IP Check Tool*, having analysed a total of 4272 dependencies (3rd party libraries used) in the CODECO repository. An automatic report is generated, as shown in Figure 12, which indicates:

- **Location:** file which indicates the library generating the potentially problematic 3rd party library.
- **Name:** library used in the CODECO code, which potentially causes the issue.
- **License:** license under which the 3rd party library is licensed.
- **Status:** status of the dependency according to the corresponding authority.
- **Authority:** entity assessing how the 3rd party library used is properly licensed under an open-source license and follows the best open-source practices; normally, it will be Clearly Defined¹⁹ or the Eclipse Management Organization²⁰ (EMO).
- **Verification:** In case the status is “restricted”, the result of a manual verification.

17 <https://github.com/eclipse/dash-licenses>

18 <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/research-eclipse/ip-check>

19 <https://clearlydefined.io/>

20 <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipsefdn/emo-team>

IP Check Report

Export All Search 🔍 ⌵ ⌵

Location	Name	License	Status	Authority	Verification
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-gnns/STGNN_controller/inference/requirements.txt	pypi/pypi/-/flask/3.0.0	BSD-2-Clause AND BSD-3-Clause	approved	clearlydefined	-
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-gnns/STGNN_controller/inference/requirements.txt	pypi/pypi/-/kubernetes/27.2.0	Apache-2.0	approved	clearlydefined	-
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-gnns/STGNN_controller/inference/requirements.txt	pypi/pypi/-/numpy/1.23.5	BSD-2-Clause	restricted	clearlydefined	verified
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-gnns/STGNN_controller/inference/requirements.txt	pypi/pypi/-/pandas/2.0.3	BSD-2-Clause AND BSD-3-Clause	restricted	clearlydefined	verified
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-gnns/STGNN_controller/inference/requirements.txt	pypi/pypi/-/requests-oauthlib/1.3.1	BSD-2-Clause AND ISC	restricted	clearlydefined	verified
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-gnns/STGNN_controller/inference/requirements.txt	pypi/pypi/-/requests/2.31.0	Apache-2.0 AND MIT AND Apache-2.0	approved	#13074	-
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-gnns/STGNN_controller/orchestrator/requirements.txt	pypi/pypi/-/kubernetes/27.2.0	Apache-2.0	approved	clearlydefined	-
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-gnns/STGNN_controller/orchestrator/requirements.txt	pypi/pypi/-/numpy/1.23.5	BSD-2-Clause	restricted	clearlydefined	verified
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-gnns/STGNN_controller/orchestrator/requirements.txt	pypi/pypi/-/pandas/2.0.3	BSD-2-Clause AND BSD-3-Clause	restricted	clearlydefined	verified
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-gnns/STGNN_controller/orchestrator/requirements.txt	pypi/pypi/-/requests/2.31.0	Apache-2.0 AND MIT AND Apache-2.0	approved	#13074	-

Figure 12. Snapshot of the report analysing the dependencies in the CODECO code.

Out of those 4272 dependencies, just seven required further work. For each one, an issue was created in CODECO Research Labs and assigned to the developer, following the procedure explained above. The seven issues in the repository are listed in Figure 13 (along with other issues corresponding to the application of the open-source good practices). The developers reviewed the issues and looked for a solution. In some cases, updating the library to the latest version or moving to an alternative library, in case the used one is deprecated, can solve the issue. All these IP issues were resolved and closed.

Finally, similarly to the application of the open-source best practices, as mentioned before in Section 4.2.2 *Repository Best Practices Implementation*, the CODECO Open-Source Toolkit is in evolution, and therefore, the next IP Review will be conducted directly within the final hosting environment for the Eclipse KuDECO code on GitLab, by the Eclipse EMO.

Figure 13. Issues in the CODECO Research Labs corresponding to IP dependencies or the application of the open-source good practices.

4.4 Training

To facilitate the open-source work for the partners and to help understand the open-source best practices, OSS training have been provided to the CODECO consortium. Three OSS training sessions were provided during the first two reporting periods (M7 to M24), while a last training on Open-source Business Models was provided to the consortium during the third reporting period (M24 to M39). During the central part of the project, the focus was on the implementation of the open-source best practices, while during the last year of the project, more attention was brought to the exploitation of the CODECO OSS Toolkit, as explained in Section 6. Table 3 gathers the training provided to the CODECO consortium.

Table 3. Training on open-source best practices provided to the CODECO consortium.

Name	Topics	Date
Open-source Ecosystem	Introduction to the main aspects of doing successful open-source, including governance, IP and license management, community building, and infrastructure for open collaboration; best practices from experience in doing open-source in research projects	February 2023

Name	Topics	Date
Open-source Licensing and Compliance	Introduction to open-source software licenses; categories of OSS licenses and major features; license compliance and compatibility; recommendations for CODECO open-source components	June 2023
Open Collaboration, Open Development	Open collaboration; Intellectual Property and Copyright; how to develop in the Eclipse open-source ecosystem through Research Labs	November 2023
Open-source Business Models	Open-Source Business Models. How can you make money out of it, if it's free? Successful open-source business models and examples.	April 2025

5 Achieving Sustainability: Eclipse KuDECO

This section details the strategic evolution of the CODECO research results into a long-term, sustainable open-source ecosystem. The transition from a time-bound Horizon Europe research project to a formal project under the Eclipse Foundation represents a core pillar of the CODECO project's exploitation and sustainability strategy.

5.1 From Research Prototype to Eclipse KuDECO

Figure 14: Eclipse KuDECO logo designed and chosen by the CODECO consortium.

As the CODECO project progressed through its maturity phase, from M25 to M39, it was agreed by the consortium that the CODECO Open-Source Toolkit required a governance model capable of outliving the funded research period. To ensure the orchestration framework remains maintained and continues to attract external contributors, the partners initiated the transition to the Eclipse Foundation.

The project was rebranded as Eclipse KuDECO, a name that maintains the heritage of the research project while signalling its identity as a K8s-native DECO (Decentralised Edge-Cloud Orchestration) framework. By moving to a professional open-source foundation, the project ensures that the core innovations become production-ready assets for the global developer community.

As part of the process, a logo was required. It represents the visual identity of the project. Different possibilities were designed and presented to the CODECO consortium (by the coordinator, FOR, and the dissemination manager, INO), and one was finally voted and selected, depicted in **Error! Reference source not found.**

5.2 The Eclipse Onboarding Process

The transition followed the formal **Eclipse Development Process (EDP)**²¹, moving through several regulated phases (as depicted in Figure 15) to ensure transparency and intellectual property (IP) integrity:

²¹ https://www.eclipse.org/projects/dev_process/

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- Public Discussion and Collaboration:** The technical and administrative roadmap for the transition was socialized via the Eclipse GitLab environment²², allowing for a transparent dialogue between the research consortium and the Eclipse Management Organization (EMO).
- Project Proposal:** A formal proposal was published in July 2025, detailing the project's intent, scope, and initial technical contributions. This proposal served as a call for community feedback and additional participation. The proposal is publicly available (displayed in Figure 16) and can be found in the Eclipse Foundation website²³.
- Creation Review:** Following a successful review of the proposal and the underlying code provenance, the project was officially "Provisioned." This included the transition of the primary repository from the Research Labs namespace to its permanent home.

Figure 15. Workflow for starting a project at the Eclipse Foundation.

22 <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipsefdn/emo-team/emo/-/issues/1081>

23 <https://projects.eclipse.org/proposals/eclipse-kudeco>

Eclipse KuDECO

Monday, July 21, 2025 - 20:05 by Rute C. Sofia

Basics

This proposal is in the Project Proposal Phase (as defined in the [Eclipse Development Process](#)) and is written to declare its intent and scope. We solicit additional participation and input from the community. Please login and add your feedback in the comments section.

Project
Eclipse KuDECO

Parent Project
Eclipse Technology

Proposal State
Created

Proposal

**ECLIPSE
INCUBATION**

Background

The evolution of computing from centralized Cloud infrastructures to heterogeneous, decentralised Edge environments has introduced new levels of complexity in orchestrating distributed resources. Traditional orchestration frameworks are often ill-equipped to handle the dynamic, resource-constrained, and context-sensitive nature of edge-cloud systems. As applications demand lower latency, higher resilience, and adaptive deployment strategies, new orchestration paradigms are required.

The Horizon Europe CODECO (Cognitive Decentralised Edge-Cloud Orchestration) project is a research-driven initiative aimed at enabling intelligent, autonomous orchestration across the IoT-Edge-Cloud (CEI) continuum. The project leverages cognitive computing principles—such as reasoning, learning, and knowledge representation—to provide self-adaptive, policy-aware coordination of services and infrastructure.

Developed within the Eclipse Research Labs, CODECO (codeco-project) incorporates modular components that support automated decision-making for service placement, configuration, monitoring, and adaptation, as a Kubernetes framework. It builds on formal models, semantic technologies, and decentralized control strategies to address challenges such as dynamic resource allocation, interoperability, and fault tolerance in edge-cloud environments.

KuDECO reflects the CODECO assets composed of a set of open-source tools to support the deployment of containerized applications across multi-provider federated environments. By proposing KuDECO as an Eclipse project, we aim to foster an open, collaborative platform for researchers, developers, and system architects working on next-generation orchestration solutions. Its integration within the Eclipse ecosystem will promote standardization, reusability, and extensibility, while enabling synergies with complementary projects in cloud management, model-based engineering, and AI for systems.

Scope

Eclipse KuDECO provides an open, extensible platform for the intelligent orchestration of distributed systems across edge and cloud infrastructures. Its primary goal is to enable cognitive, decentralized decision-making for deploying, configuring, and adapting services in highly dynamic and heterogeneous environments.

KuDECO focuses on the following key areas:

- **Cognitive Orchestration**
Decentralised AI techniques that apply reasoning, learning, and knowledge-based inference to automate orchestration tasks, including containerized application placement recommendations to the scheduler, scaling, and reconfiguration/migration.
- **Decentralised Control Models**
Architectures that support distributed decision-making across Edge nodes, Cloud environments, reducing dependency on central control and enabling resilience and autonomy.
- **Semantic Configuration and Policies**

RELATED PROJECTS

Project Hierarchy:

- Eclipse Technology
 - Eclipse KuDECO

Figure 16. Snapshot of the Eclipse KuDECO Project Proposal.

5.3 Initial Project Committers

The sustainability of an open-source project is driven by its "Committers"—the individuals with the authority to influence the code base and manage technical contributions. The initial list of committers for Eclipse KuDECO represents a diverse group of researchers and engineers from the CODECO partners. The next two tables list the project leaders, Table 4, and initial project committers, Table 5; these lists include the initial contributors defined during the proposal phase, which are expected to grow as external stakeholders join the Eclipse KuDECO community.

Table 4. Eclipse KuDECO Project Leaders

Project Lead	Organisation
Rute C. Sofia	FOR
Tina Samizadeh	FOR

Table 5. Eclipse KuDECO Initial Committers

Committers	Organisation
Rute C. Sofia	FOR
Tina Samizadeh	FOR
Pepi Paraskevoulakou	UPRC
Panagiotis Karamolegkos	UPRC
Dean Kelly	RHT
Alka Nixon	RHT
Josh Salomon	RHT
Alejandro Espinosa	I2CAT
Rizkallah Touma	I2CAT
Jürgen Gesswein	SIE
Guillermo S. Illán	TID
Borja Dorado Nogales	UC3M
Alejandro Tjaarda De Cock Buning	UC3M
George Koukis	ATH
David Remon	ECL
Alberto del Río	UPM
Miguel Ángel Puentes	UPM

5.4 Sustainability Plan and Asset Governance

The CODECO project's primary technical output is being transitioned into **Eclipse KuDECO**, an open-source K8s-oriented framework for intelligent, adaptive orchestration of containerised applications across distributed Edge-Cloud environments. Currently in incubating state under the Eclipse Technology top-level project and licensed under the Apache Software License 2.0, Eclipse KuDECO represents the long-term vehicle through which the innovations developed within CODECO will be maintained, evolved, and made available to the wider community beyond the project's lifetime.

The central challenge now facing the consortium is ensuring that this transition results in a genuinely self-sustaining open-source project — one that does not depend on continued EU funding, is not reliant on any single individual or organisation, and is capable of attracting real users and external contributors over time. This section outlines the governance framework, partner commitments, and three-year operational plan designed to achieve this.

5.4.1 Sustainability Criteria

For Eclipse KuDECO to be considered self-sustaining at the end of the three-year plan, it must satisfy the following conditions, drawn from established Eclipse Foundation guidance on successful open-source project governance:

- **Multiple maintainers.** Responsibility for the codebase is distributed across at least two independent organizations, such that the departure of any individual does not threaten continuity.

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- **Real users.** The project has documented adopters beyond the original consortium, ideally including external pilots or integration cases.
- **Predictable releases.** A regular, publicly communicated release cadence is in place and has been demonstrated over at least two cycles.
- **Clear governance.** Decision-making processes, committer rights, and contribution procedures are documented, publicly accessible, and actively followed.
- **Financial independence.** The project's operational continuity does not depend on EU project funding or any single sponsor.

5.4.2 Governance Framework

FOR is leading the development of a proposed governance document for Eclipse KuDECO, building on the existing consortium agreement, which partners should verify remains sufficient as a foundation, and extending it with a dedicated governance layer appropriate to the post-project context. Key elements of this framework include:

- **Meeting cadence.** A minimum of one governance meeting per semester beyond the project lifetime, dedicated to discussing reuse, planning releases, and reviewing the health of the community.
- **Committer structure.** A defined set of committers has been identified. Partners are asked to confirm the specific named contacts from their organizations who can genuinely commit to fulfilling this role on an ongoing basis and to flag any gaps or missing maintainers by contacting the project lead. It is essential that committer responsibilities are not concentrated on one person.
- **Governance documentation.** The governance plan is published and maintained on the Eclipse KuDECO project governance page, with the first three years of maintenance commitments explicitly described. Partners are encouraged to review this and raise any concerns.
- **Repository transition.** The project repository is transitioning to the Eclipse KuDECO GitLab space. Partners should ensure their contributions and documentation are aligned with this new home.
- **Community identity.** A key open question requiring consortium input is: who constitutes the KuDECO community beyond the current partners, and how can it be grown and retained? This requires a deliberate outreach strategy developed in collaboration with the Eclipse Foundation.

5.4.3 Three-year Operational Plan

5.4.3.1 Year 1 (2026): Establish Governance and Community

The priority in the first year is to put in place the structural and technical foundations that will allow the project to operate independently and attract its first external contributors.

- **Governance and operations.** Formally define and publish the committer and maintainer list. Establish and document the decision-making process — whether based on lazy consensus, formal voting, or a hybrid model. Publish the governance documentation and initiate operations according to the agreed cadence: a minimum of one release per year and one governance meeting per semester.
- **Technical consolidation.** Clean the repository by removing dead or deprecated code; update dependencies to current stable versions; ensure build reproducibility; establish a CI/CD pipeline; and introduce minimal security scanning as a baseline for ongoing compliance.
- **Community engagement.** Make a public announcement of Eclipse KuDECO at the CODECO final event and through the Eclipse Foundation channels. Publish clean, complete documentation — targeted for completion by May 2026. Add a CONTRIBUTING.md file to

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lower the barrier for new contributors. Publish a clear project roadmap. Invite external contributors from adjacent communities, coordinating with the Eclipse Foundation on outreach strategy.

- **Funding strategy.** Identify and apply for follow-on EU projects or national funding programmes that could provide a bridge for continued development. Begin exploratory discussions with the Eclipse Foundation regarding the potential path towards an Eclipse Working Group, which would provide a more structured industry collaboration framework and access to member resources.

5.4.3.2 Year 2 (2027): Grow and Validate

With governance in place, the focus shifts to demonstrating real-world adoption and evolving the architecture based on user feedback.

- **Adoption focus.** Identify and engage three to five pilot users from outside the original consortium. Establish a structured feedback mechanism and collect user experience data. Publish at least one case study documenting a real adoption of Eclipse KuDECO, providing evidence of value to prospective adopters and funders alike.
- **Architecture evolution.** Based on user feedback and community input, modularize the codebase where needed; define clear extension points to make the framework easier to integrate and build upon; and improve API stability to give downstream users a reliable foundation. Deliver a mature 1.x release, accompanied by improved documentation, as the primary technical milestone of the year. Track and report on the involvement of any external maintainers who have joined the project.
- **Funding and sustainability review.** Assess the status of any funding applications made in Year 1. Review the feasibility of the Eclipse Working Group path based on the level of industry engagement achieved.

5.4.3.3 Year 3 (2028): Consolidate and Secure

The third year focuses on long-term resilience, re-evaluating what is working, addressing structural risks, and ensuring the project is equipped to handle the responsibilities of a mature open-source project.

- **Governance review.** Revisit the governance structure considering three years of operational experience: re-evaluate the composition of the maintainer group, assess whether decision-making processes are functioning effectively, and make any necessary adjustments to ensure the project remains distributed and resilient.
- **Security and compliance.** Establish a formal vulnerability reporting and response policy, aligned with Eclipse Foundation security guidelines. Ensure that the project has access to ongoing security scanning and dependency monitoring, and that processes are in place to handle disclosures responsibly and transparently.
- **Long-term positioning.** By the end of Year 3, the project should be able to present a credible case for continued relevance, whether through a formal Eclipse Working Group structure, integration with a broader industry initiative, or demonstrated self-sustaining community activity.

5.4.3.4 Commitment by Partners

The following actions have been agreed upon by the Partners involved, comprising the consortium:

- **Confirm named committers** — provide specific contacts who can genuinely fulfil ongoing committer responsibilities; send details to the project lead, copying David and Marco

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- **Review the governance document** — check the proposed governance for completeness and flag any missing maintainers or concerns.
- **Verify the consortium agreement** — confirm that the existing agreement provides a sufficient basis for the post-project governance structure.
- **Contribute to the community strategy** — share ideas and contacts for growing the KuDECO user and contributor base beyond the current consortium.
- **Declare partner commitments** — indicate the level of contribution (developer time, maintenance effort, infrastructure) each partner can realistically sustain over the three-year plan without EU project funding.

5.5 Governance and Long-Term Sustainability Guidance

By establishing Eclipse KuDECO as a formal project, the results of the CODECO project now benefit from:

- **Neutral Governance:** Managed under the Eclipse Foundation's bylaws, preventing vendor lock-in and encouraging industry-wide collaboration.
- **Professional IP Management:** All code is licensed under Apache License 2.0, facilitating its use in both commercial and academic environments.
- **Professional Infrastructure:** Use of the Eclipse GitLab (hosting) and CI/CD tools ensures that the software meets professional-grade quality and security standards.

The transition effectively moves CODECO from a research "deliverable" to a living "product," providing a clear path for exploitation and further innovation beyond the official project end date.

The creation of Eclipse KuDECO was publicly announced and posted on different social media²⁴ platforms. **Error! Reference source not found.**, shows part of the announcement.

Figure 17: partial view on the new Eclipse KuDECO project announcement.

Among the resources that the Eclipse KuDECO project has received for its creation, there are: an issue tracker, a GitLab instance, a mailing list and a project website.

6 OSS Community-building Year 3

This section summarises the community-building activities done during the last reporting period: M25 – M39.

During the initial phase, the main goal was to set up the infrastructure to allow the consortium to develop in an open and collaborative way. During the second phase, the main objective was to implement the open-source best practices while community-building activities were developed, focussing on starting the gathering of a community around CODECO, with the strong intention to make an impact with the open source; completely specifying the CODECO Toolkit and defining the framework architecture, under WP3, was a key milestone (see deliverable D10 [4]). During this last phase, the development of the CODECO Open-Source Toolkit has concluded, and main objective has been the sustainability of the project, trying to contribute back to the community the main developments and CODECO achievements.

The CODECO results comprise five major assets, of which three are most relevant for the open-source and community-building approach:

²⁴ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/eclipse-foundation_eclipsefdn-kudeco-opensource-activity-7425163857494654976-GmPX

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- **A2 Open-source Eclipse Repository:** A developer-oriented open-source software repository, to be available in an early stage of the project, thus allowing for early exploitation of initial, advanced results and a better adaptation throughout the project lifetime.
- **A3 Training Database:** Learning Hub, composed of training tools and events, to support the development of services based on the CODECO framework.
- **A5 Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme (IRCEP):** Multiple community events, based on the different use-cases and including different CODECO stakeholders.

Section 4.1.1 explained how the CODECO open repository has been set up in the Eclipse Research Labs, in GitLab. Along with it, to facilitate the adoption of the open-source approach by the project partners, several learning resources have been provided, including the set of training and videos provided under task T7.3. These actions have addressed the first two assets, A2 and A3, while A5 will be addressed in this section, where we will list the actions done with the main goal of engaging with the developers and creating a community around CODECO. This includes the following activities as described in Task 7.1:

- **Development of liaisons with relevant open-source projects and initiatives**, along with interaction with the EUCloudEdgeIoT²⁵ Research Community, as well as other European initiatives, such as HiPEAC²⁶ and AIOTI²⁷.
- **Participation in OSS community events**, e.g., Open Community Experience (OCX), DevConf 2025²⁸, or the CODECO Hackathon.
- **Production of open-source specific communication materials** (logo, posters, stickers, etc.), contribution to the relevant channels (social media, blog, Eclipse newsletter), etc.

These task objectives have been addressed, as will be shown in section 6.2, where the communication activities and events done during the last 15 months are displayed. The CODECO Hackathon was organised and executed in M29, as detailed in Section 6.3.1.1. The IRCEP organised different activities and challenges, facilitating the approach to the community. Section 6.1 puts the CODECO target groups in the perspective of open source.

6.1 Target Communities

CODECO has defined in its GA the target stakeholders. To outreach, the CODECO Deliverable *D21 – Dissemination, Communication, Promotion Plan* [7] explains the key activities planned for each target stakeholder group. These groups, from their own perspectives, may be interested in the open-source part of the project:

- **Information and communication technologies (ICT):** Industrial and small and medium-sized enterprises (SME) players; vendors and integrators, service providers and telecommunications operators.
For ICT companies, open source is a means to save money, resources, attract developers and foster innovation. ICT will keep an eye on the available open-source tools for their own projects, products, or services.
- **Government, municipalities, public authorities, and policymakers (GOV):** A wide group of public sector stakeholders including government agencies, regulators, municipalities, citizens, public authorities, and other organizations.

²⁵ <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/>

²⁶ <https://www.hipeac.net/>

²⁷ <https://aioti.eu/>

²⁸ <https://www.devconf.info/cz/>

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For GOV, it is important to build knowledge regarding open-source to address the need for vendor-neutral public infrastructure, to avoid vendor-lock in and reach some degree of digital sovereignty.

- **Standardization entities and open-source communities (SDO):** Standardization entities responsible for defining and maintaining standards for various industries and technologies. Normative, pre-normative entities and with open-source alliances and consortia will collaborate on the development and adoption of innovative technologies and open-source software, relevant to the CODECO ecosystem.
- **Academia and research (AR):** Research scientists, teachers, and students in the field of computer science, engineering, and related disciplines. AR are a key group to spread the benefits of the CODECO concept.
It is key to educate the next generation IT experts and equip them with the open-source skills required for careers in industry and academia alike. CODECO will be a vehicle to perform this kind of education and vice-versa benefit from the innovation potential that is inherent to this stakeholder group.
- **End-users (EUS):** The public and specific end-users in the use-case domains, including consumers, who are interested in learning about the latest developments in Edge-Cloud computing and IoT and how these technologies will impact their lives.
CODECO open-source results may be exploited in future products or services for EUS. It allows them to freely experiment with the latest innovations.
- **Developers (DEV):** Software developers and early developers with whom CODECO can interact via the activities developed in, among others, WP7 (community-building, Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme for third-party engagement) will be considered to promote and evaluate the CODECO toolkit and accelerate the integration of knowledge.
Software developers are the key target group when aiming to build a community of open-source developers around CODECO.
- **Public in General (Pub):** General audience may also be considered as stakeholders of CODECO. Even without a specialized background in the technical areas of the project, they may still be interested in CODECO and understanding its potential implications for society.

Evangelizing about open-source and creating interest and knowledge in the public is important and doing so by communicating about publicly funded innovations such as CODECO is a must.

Among these groups, defined as target audience, the community-building activities are developed with the focus on two groups, **open-source communities (SDO)** and **developers (DEV)** and keeping in mind also the other relevant groups, such as **ICT**, **GOV** or **EUS**.

We have already put effort into explaining it in this document in **Section 2**: open source is inherently linked to software developers since it started; the creators of open source were software developers (**DEV**), and this group requires special attention. When it comes to our CODECO research project, the same principle applies: “*Don’t forget the developers.*” This group has the capacity to make CODECO sustainable.

Most of the open-source communication activities and events done in CODECO have been focused on the developers, trying to create a community around the CODECO Toolkit, which could use and maintain the code. This gets special relevance as the Eclipse KuDECO project is live now. The following section provides an overview of the measures implemented during the CODECO lifetime, focusing specifically on the current reporting period M25-M39.

6.2 Community-building Activities and Impact

This section gathers the community building activities performed during the third and last year of the CODECO project’s lifetime.

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Table 6 summarises the main activities performed in CODECO during the whole project lifetime, under the “community-building” umbrella, with special focus to the ones implemented between M25 and M39, as the activities during M1-M24 had already been duly reported in the previous versions of this document, and can be found in the Annex 1 (Section 8) and Annex 2 (Section 9).

Typically, open-source community activities contribute to a range of communication and dissemination categories and related KPIs as explained in the CODECO Deliverable *D21 – Dissemination, Communication, Promotion Plan* [7]. The next table shows, among the dissemination activities for the CODECO project, their measures of impact listed in that Deliverable, the specific KPIs regarding open-source and the contribution to them from the open-source perspective.

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Table 6. Open-source community-building activities held until M39.

Activity	Targets	Aim	KPIs (D21)	Lead/Contributors	OSS Contributions	Impact
Media dissemination	All	Dissemination of the overall project development via broad media, e.g., TV, podcasts, YouTube videos, public magazines, and journals.	1 per year	FOR, ECL, INO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website. - Involvement in EUCEI. - EclipseCon2023 CODECO video. - OCX 2024. - Zenodo community²⁹ - YouTube³⁰. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website: 17,000 views corresponding to 6100 visitors. - Zenodo: +8,300 views and +8,000 downloads across all documents; 1,632 views and 1479 downloads with focus on the deliverables related with OSS. - YouTube: +850 views in the CODECO exclusive channel.
Press releases	All	Dissemination about the overall project development, results, and events.	4 per year (multiple partners) reaching to over 500 end-users.	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ECL newsletter 2023. - FOR online press releases. - Social network activities with focus on OSS. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Eclipse newsletter: over 250000 subscribers. - FOR press releases (x2): over 200 views. - Social networks: 662 followers in LinkedIn; 657 in X (former Twitter) .
Industrial Event	DEV, ICT, AR	1 Inception event, industrial workshop (M12) Organised by FOR having as main target industrial stakeholders and aiming at igniting interest in further exploring the use-cases in multiple fields of IoT/Edge.	>50 participants	All	HiPEAC industrial workshops: first one on 01.2024, second one on 01.2025, third one. on 01.2026	Industrial Workshops: average participation of 55-65 attendees including students, researchers and SMEs.

²⁹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/he-codeco>

³⁰ First video added in M11 (November 2023).

Activity	Targets	Aim	KPIs (D21)	Lead/Contributors	OSS Contributions	Impact
Representation in events	ICT, AR, SDO, EUS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disseminate CODECO results in different venues, industrial and scientific. - Promotion of active participation and discussions on exploitation aspects and community-building. 	>50 events	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EclipseCon, Ludwigsburg, Germany, Oct. 2023. - Eclipse eSAAM on Cloud to Edge Continuum: October 2023 and October 2024. - 6G CONASENSE workshop, co-located with IEEE WPMC2023, Orlando, USA, Nov 2023. - WF-IoT 2023, Aveiro, Portugal, October 2023. - Nexus Forum 2023, Brussels, Belgium, Oct. 2023. - AI-SPRINT final event, online, Oct 2023. - Embedded World 2024, Nuremberg, Germany, April 2024. - RedHat Summit, Boston, USA, May 2025. - Dev.Conf.CZ, Brno, Czechia, June 2024 and June 2025. - EUCNC CONASENSE 2024, Antwerpen, Belgium, June 2024. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -EclipseCon: > 200 participants. - 6G CONASENSE: 40 participants. - MobiArch 2023: 30 participants. - WF-IoT 2023: 70 participants. - Nexus Forum 2023: >100 participants. - AI-SPRINT final event: 70 participants. - Embedded World 2024 : >100 participants. - RedHat Summit : >450 participants. - DevConf.CZ : >100 participants. - EUCNC CONASENSE 2024 : 60 participants. - IETF Hackathon: >150 participants. - Software Crafters: +500 participants. - Open-Source Community Day: 70 participants.

Activity	Targets	Aim	KPIs (D21)	Lead/Contributors	OSS Contributions	Impact
					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CODECO Hackathon (IETF), Madrid, Spain, July 2025. - Open-Source Experience (OCX) 2024, Mainz Germany, Oct. 2024 - Open-Source Community Day 2025, Madrid, Spain, October 2025. - Software Crafters 2025, Barcelona, Spain, Oct. 2025 - Fortiss Demo Camp, Oct 2025. 	
Advanced training ³¹	ICT, AR, DEV, SDO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transfer results and address potential gaps derived from interaction with the scientific community. - Specific events and participation in community events, e.g., summer schools, Webinars, workshops. 	>20 organized training events with at least 50 participants	INTRA, ECL, UPRC, FOR, UPM, ATH, UGOE, I2CAT.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 4 trainings provided by ECL on open source (Table 3). - CODECO Hackathon - IRCEP Local Events at UPRC, UPM, ATH, UGOE, I2CAT. - Learning Hub, available online. 	All partners involved, average of 40 persons in each workshop.
CODECO GitLab Repository	DEV, ICT, AR	Re-use of OSS code. Community engagement.	N/A	ECL, All	- Early release of OSS code as defined in D11, M10.	- 69 developers registered in the CODECO Research Labs in GitLab.

³¹ Advanced training activities in CODECO have been developed under task T7.4. Moreover, partner Eclipse has provided training internally for the consortium, to bootstrap an understanding of building results towards OSS.

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Activity	Targets	Aim	KPIs (D21)	Lead/ Contributors	OSS Contributions	Impact
					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CODECO Open-source Toolkit, and in D12. - Continuous development, open and transparent collaboration. - Continuous releases of code in GitLab. - Eclipse KuDECO, final release of the CODECO Toolkit into formal open-source project. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Eclipse Foundation Community receiving Eclipse KuDECO project.

Additionally, the next subsections provide more information, including the measure of impact, for some of those actions. For each activity, a brief description and an assessment of its impact on the CODECO community-building are provided.

6.3 Media Dissemination and Press Releases

Having in mind the focus of OSS community-building, several efforts have been made, as described in Table 6:

- Across the CODECO LinkedIn space, partner INO has been driving several dissemination activities, covering OSS results of the project, such as software release, among others. CODECO LinkedIn has a total of 2585 page views with 657 followers.
- The Website has reached 6,100 visitors, corresponding to a total of 17,000 views.
- The CODECO Zenodo community has reached a total of 8,300 views and 8,000 downloads, increasing by more than 150% the total number of views and downloads from the previous reporting period.
- Different press releases have reached over two hundred views.
- CODECO's exclusive YouTube Channel, with 67 videos having been uploaded to it, totaling more than 850 views and 23 subscribers.

6.3.1 OSS Oriented Events

Key events have been held during the third and last year of project life, 2025, oriented to the DEV, AR, and ICT stakeholder groups:

- **DevConf2025³²**, organized by RHT, in Brno, Czech Republic, 12th – 14th June 2025. Targets were DEV, AR, and ICT. Javier Castillo, Dean Kelly and Alka Nixon (RHT) had the opportunity to give a talk, as depicted in Figure 18. More than 1,500 attendees registered at the event, >100 participants attending the CODECO talk, making it an opportunity to meet the developer community.
- **CODECO Hackathon**, whose targets were AR, DEV, ICT and SDO, detailed in the next section, Section 6.3.1.1.
- **Universidad Complutense de Madrid**, in November 2025, targeting AR and DEV. David Remon (ECL) explained the main functionalities of CODECO and detailed the IRCEP challenges to more than 230 Engineering students by David Remon (ECL), as can be seen in Figure 20.
- **Red Hat Summit³³**, an event organized by RHT, where the targets are DEV, AR, and ICT. CODECO was present in Boston, 19th – 22nd May 2025, where Javier Castillo (RHT) explained the main functionalities of the CODECO Toolkit. Figure 19 shows a capture of the talk.
- **ICPE2025³⁴**, and more specifically, the HotCloudPerf workshop organized co-located with the main event in Toronto, Canada, on 6th May 2025. Javier Castillo (RHT) explained CODECO to the attendees, as depicted in Figure 21. Targets were DEV, AT and ICT.
- **Software Crafters 2025³⁵**, organized by ECL in Barcelona, Spain, 24th – 25th October 2025. Targets were DEV, AR and ICT. Around 450 attendees at this event, where David Remon (ECL) presented CODECO to the developers, and more specifically the IRCEP challenges available at that moment, as can be seen in Figure 22.

³² <https://www.devconf.info/cz/>

³³ <https://www.redhat.com/en/summit>

³⁴ <https://icpe2025.spec.org/>

³⁵ <https://softwarecrafters.barcelona/>

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- **Open-Source Community Day 2025³⁶**, organized by ECL in Madrid, Spain, 23rd – 24th September 2025, in collaboration with CEI-Sphere³⁷ (part of EUCloudEdgeloT.eu) and targeting AR, ICT, and SDO. Rute Sofia (FOR) had a session where she explained CODECO's methodology and assets to the attendees, as depicted in Figure 23.
- **AIOTI Days 2025³⁸**, organized by the Alliance for IoT and Edge Computing Innovation (AIOTI), in Madrid, Spain, 22nd – 23rd September 2025. Targets were DEV, AR, and ICT. Rute C. Sofia presented CODECO's architecture and its experimental framework. The workshop focused on the exploration of how the continuum and digital twins meet virtual worlds in industrial space, creating a physical-digital virtual continuum.

Figure 18. Javier Castillo presenting CODECO at DevConf Europe 2025.

Figure 19. Javier Castillo introduced CODECO at the Red Hat Summit 2025.

36 <https://www.eclipse.org/events/2025/oscd/>

37 <https://ceisphere.eu/>

38 <https://aioti.eu/aioti-days-2025/>

Figure 20. David Remon presenting CODECO at Universidad Complutense de Madrid.

Figure 21. Javier Castillo at the HotCloudPerf workshop, co-located with the ICPE 2025.

Figure 22. David Remon explaining the IRCEP program to the developers at Software Crafters.

Figure 23. Rute Sofia explaining CODECO’s methodology and assets to the audience.

6.3.1.1 CODECO Hackathon

CODECO organized one of its main community-building events, the CODECO Hackathon, in July 2025. This event was strategically integrated into the IETF 123 meeting held in Madrid³⁹, Spain, from July 19 to 25, 2025. By aligning with a globally recognized standardization body like the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF), the project was able to bridge the gap between cutting-edge research, open-source development, and international internet standards, enhancing the work done on Standardization under the task T6.2.

39 <https://datatracker.ietf.org/meeting/123/proceedings/>

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Context: The IETF and the IETF Hackathon

The Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) is the premier international organization responsible for developing open standards that power the global internet. Unlike traditional academic conferences or industrial trade shows, the IETF operates on a model of "rough consensus and running code," prioritizing practical implementations alongside theoretical specifications.

The IETF Hackathon⁴⁰, held on the weekend preceding the main IETF working group sessions, is an example and contributor of this philosophy. It provides a collaborative, non-competitive environment where developers and researchers work together to develop utilities and solutions that demonstrate real-world implementations of emerging internet protocols. The IETF 123 Hackathon attracted 682 participants (597 on-site in Madrid and 85 remote) working on over 60 distinct projects. The next picture, Figure 24 shows the collaborative atmosphere which characterizes this event.

Figure 24. CODECO's presence at the IETF 123 Hackathon.

Planning and Organization: The CODECO consortium worked on the hackathon under task T7.1. It started with the planning of the hackathon six months in advance, continued with the organisation and concluded with the execution and presence of CODECO at the IETF 123 Hackathon. The goal was to leverage the high concentration of software engineers and protocol experts at IETF 123 to increase awareness of the CODECO Open-Source Toolkit.

The organization followed the IETF "Champion" model, where project leads, the Champions, volunteer to mentor participants and guide the technical work throughout the intensive two-day session. Figure 25 shows the CODECO team, including the CODECO Champions, present at the Hackathon to support developers and disseminate the project. To maximize engagement, CODECO prepared technical documentation and code snippets in advance, making them available through the Eclipse Research Labs repository⁴¹.

⁴⁰ <https://wiki.ietf.org/en/meeting/123/hackathon>

⁴¹ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/hackathon>

Figure 25. CODECO partners supporting the developers and representing CODECO at the Hackathon.

CODECO Challenges at the Hackathon: CODECO implemented three technical challenges⁴² for the hackathon, focused on the integration of cognitive orchestration with networking and compute metrics, having two of them finally presented and resolved at the CODECO hackathon. These challenges were designed to test the robustness of the CODECO framework in a diverse, heterogeneous environment and to gather feedback from external experts. Figure 26 shows a group of developers working on the challenges during the CODECO hackathon. The developed challenges were:

Challenge 1 — Green Network Observability and Reporting (challenge-GREEN): Participants enhanced CODECO to monitor and report energy consumption across edge-cloud infrastructure in a format compatible with the IETF GREEN working group's emerging informational draft. The goal was to collect real-time power metrics from devices, PDUs, and servers and expose them through CODECO's orchestration layer as meaningful sustainability data across multi-domain deployments.

Challenge 2 — Joint Exposure of Compute and Network Metrics for Path Selection (challenge-CATS): Participants extended CODECO with CATS-aligned (Computing-Aware Traffic Steering) path selection. CODECO's ACM and NetMA components collect real-time CPU, memory, latency, and congestion metrics, which PDLC-CA aggregates into node and cluster scores. The challenge tasked participants with using those scores to drive compute-aware traffic steering consistent with the IETF CATS working group's metric-definition draft.

⁴² <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/hackathon>

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Challenge 3 — Benchmarking Network-aware Edge-Cloud Orchestration with CODEF:

Participants used CODEF (the CODECO Experimentation Framework) to run structured benchmarks of CODECO's orchestration across heterogeneous edge-cloud infrastructure, jointly measuring network and compute dimensions during workload placement, migration, and resource allocation. This was the challenge that was scoped and prepared but not brought to completion and presentation at the final hackathon session.

Due to limited possibility of partners to support a Hackathon over a weekend, two primary challenges presented were:

- **Benchmarking with Network-Compute Metrics and Energy-Awareness across Edge-Cloud:** Participants worked on implementing and validating benchmarking tools within the CODECO framework that jointly consider network performance and computational constraints. A specific emphasis was placed on energy-awareness, challenging participants to optimize workload placement not only for latency and throughput but also for minimizing the environmental footprint of distributed Edge-Cloud operations.
- **GREEN Framework Validation:** Aligned with the IETF's focus on sustainable networking, this challenge task participants with validating the GREEN (Gauging Robust Energy Efficiency in Networks) Framework within CODECO use cases. This involved integrating APIs to report real-time energy consumption from diverse components (devices, PDUs, and servers) and validating these metrics across multi-domain Edge-Cloud deployments.

Figure 26. Developers working during the IETF-123 Hackathon.

At the end of the IETF Hackathon, each challenge has some minutes to present its results. This gave us the opportunity to introduce CODECO to the attendees, both in person and remote, and to present the work and results achieved during the weekend, as can be seen in Figure 27.

Figure 27. Presentation of the results of the CODECO challenges at the hackathon.

Impact and Outcomes

The integration of the CODECO Hackathon into IETF 123 resulted in several key outcomes:

- **Code Contributions:** Participants engaged directly with the CODECO code base, identifying bugs and proposing enhancements to the NetMA and MDM components.
- **Standards Alignment:** The challenges facilitated a direct dialogue between CODECO researchers and IETF working group members, ensuring that CODECO's approach to decentralized orchestration remains compatible with evolving internet standards.
- **Community Growth:** The event served as a "ramp-up" phase for the CODECO Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme (IRCEP), attracting new developers to the Eclipse GitLab repository and expanding the project's visibility beyond the original consortium.

6.3.1.2 IRCEP Support

CODECO's Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme (IRCEP) was designed to engage external stakeholders through a series of Experimentation and Validation challenges, published on the CODECO website and open for submissions from July 2025 to February 2026. The programme offered 11 challenges, each led by a technical partner within the consortium, covering areas such as deployment and scalability, scheduling, data generation, placement strategies, benchmarking, secure connectivity, energy-awareness, and resilience. These challenges spanned CODECO's main domains of Smart Cities, Manufacturing, Energy, and Mobility, and took the form of targeted experiments, co-creation activities, solution validation exercises, and thematic competitions. IRCEP was open to four types of participants: Small and Medium Enterprises, Early Developers, Researchers, and Students, all of whom needed to demonstrate relevant expertise and a clear alignment with CODECO's goals. To encourage participation, each selected submission was eligible for a financial award of €2,800, with up to three winners per challenge.

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Since the launch of the challenges, IRCEP has been actively promoted through a range of dissemination activities. On social media, a total of 33 LinkedIn posts related to IRCEP were published between June 2025 and February 2026, covering both the challenges as a whole and targeted posts for each local event. Posts were shared on the project's official LinkedIn page and in relevant thematic groups, with all partners also re-sharing content across their own networks to maximise reach.

Beyond social media, the IRCEP challenges were featured at the IETF Hackathon in Madrid in July 2025, providing early visibility within a technical community. An informative webinar was also held to present the IRCEP challenges to a wider audience, with the recording subsequently made available on the IRCEP page of the CODECO website and on the CODECO YouTube channel, ensuring the content remained accessible to those who could not attend live. To further encourage participation, seven local events were organised from November to February 2026, as outlined in Table 7 below. each hosted in partnership with the consortium partner responsible for the respective challenge. The IRCEP Local events were designed to inform potential participants about the specific challenge, answer questions, and encourage them to take part, with the hosting partner providing direct technical context and support. **IRCEP results are further detailed in an individual deliverable, D28.**

Table 7. Local events organised under IRCEP initiative.

Date	Challenge	Host
21 November 2025	CODECO Data Generator #1	UPRC
24 November 2025	CODECO Intelligent Recommender	I2CAT
26 November 2025	CODECO Data Generator #1	UGOE
28 November 2025	CODECO Data Generator #2	UPRC
28 November 2025	CODECO CODEF	ATH
11 December 2025	CODECO Energy / Resilience / SWM	FOR
16 February 2026	All Challenges	UPM

The challenges were also promoted at the CODECO booth at HiPEAC 2026 and at the Software Crafters Conference, as mentioned before in this Section 6.3, reaching an audience of researchers, developers, and industry professionals attending the conferences.

Additionally, the IRCEP challenges and local events were also promoted through the EUCEI Monthly News Digest and the EUCEI community platform between September 2025 and February 2026, reaching the digest's 664+ subscribers and extending visibility beyond the project's own networks to a wider European audience.

As part of the actions performed under T7.1, there has been support in terms of “logistics and infrastructure” in the CODECO Research Labs for the different challenges and activities implemented by the IRCEP program.

In close and continuous collaboration with T7.2, in charge of IRCEP, different sub-repositories were created and handled when required by the initiatives, allowing the coordinated planning and implementation of such challenges⁴³. Figure 28 shows the list of IRCEP challenges available in the CODECO Research Labs in GitLab.

⁴³ <https://he-codeco.eu/ircep/ircep-challenges/>

Eclipse Research Labs / CODECO Project / IRCEP Challenges

IRCEP Challenges

Recent activity Last 30 days: Merge requests created: 0, Issues created: 0, Members added: 0

Subgroups and projects: Shared projects, Shared groups, Inactive

Search (3 character minimum)

Project Name	Issues	Pull Requests	Members
CODECO Data Generator 1	3	1	2
CODECO Data Generator 2	12	1	2
CODECO Energy awareness Strategies	1	1	2
CODECO Intelligent Recommender 1 Load balancing with cross layer RL optimization	3	1	3
CODECO Intelligent Recommender 2 Benchmarking across diverse vertical workloads	3	1	3
CODECO Resilience Strategies Evaluation	1	1	2
CODECO Secure Connectivity	1	1	1
CODEF and Benchmarking Dynamic Stress Testing	3	1	1
CODEF and Benchmarking Security Mechanisms for CODEF	2	1	1
CODEF and Benchmarking Testing Debugging and AI powered assistant	2	1	1
Evaluate the CODECO SWM Scheduler	2	1	2

6 - Deployment and Scalability of CODECO (0 stars, 5 months ago)

Figure 28. Sub-repositories available in the CODECO Research Labs and corresponding to the IRCEP challenges.

6.3.2 Engagement in OSS Communities

In addition to the development of specific events and participation in external events, CODECO has been involved in different OSS communities, contributing to the creation of OSS paths in Europe. This section summarizes the contributions held so far.

6.3.2.1 EUCloudEdgeIoT Engagement

The EUCloudEdgeIoT.eu initiative aims to realise a pathway for the understanding and development of the Cloud, Edge and IoT continuum by promoting cooperation between a wide range of research projects, developers and suppliers, business users and potential adopters of this new technological paradigm. The initiative manages six Task Forces (TFs): TF1 Strategic Liaisons, TF2 Open-source Engagement, TF3 Architecture, TF4 Ecosystem Engagement, TF5 Market and Sectors, TF6 Communications.

Different partners in CODECO are engaging across all TFs. Specifically, FOR is involved in TF1, TF3, and TF6. ECL leads and contributes to TF2, therefore has provided input from CODECO as well. ATOS leads TF3. Moreover, INO has engaged in TF1, TF4, and TF6 in the context of the CODECO Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme (IRCEP), which started in 2024. Key contributions of CODECO in the context of

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EUCloudEdgeIoT resulted from its framework (architecture and taxonomy); OSS guidelines (TF2); use-case aspects towards SDOs (TF1).

Impact Assessment: For CODECO, the EUCloudEdgeIoT.eu initiative has been an excellent opportunity to interact and align with the cluster of similar European projects and share work and results within relevant working groups. What has been also relevant was the definition of taxonomy and the architectural view for the Edge-Cloud continuum where CODECO has been involved. For the period being reported, in addition to contributions to TF3 (taxonomy, architecture), CODECO has engaged in TF1 in the context of developed white papers, and concerning its use-cases, and novelty concerning Edge/IoT applications.

6.3.2.2 HIPEAC

The HIPEAC initiative addresses topics across the compute continuum from Edge to Cloud, HIPEAC is a network of around 2,000 world-class computing systems researchers, industry representatives, and students, i.e. the AR, ICT and DEV stakeholder of CODECO. After having organised an industrial workshop in HIPEAC 2024, CODECO prepared another workshop for the HIPEAC 2025 Conference, repeating again the organisation of a last workshop at HIPEAC 2026, profiting of the project extension. The details about CODECO's participation in HIPEAC 2024 can be found in **Section 9, Appendix 2**.

HIPEAC 2025

The second HIPEAC community initiative took place in Barcelona from 20th to 22nd of January 2025. On the last day of the event, CODECO had a dedicated session as part of a Machine Learning for Edge-Cloud Systems⁴⁴ (ML4ECS) workshop. The session was very well received by the audience and generated interesting and fruitful questions and later conversations. CODECO was present at the ECL booth during the whole event as well, gathering the attention of the attendees. The HIPEAC conference run over three days and attracted over 800 participants, achieving a participation record. The event targeted AR, ICT, and the DEV community too. Figure 29 shows one of the presentations at the workshop about the CODECO project in general, while Figure 30 shows a presentation about the PDLC component. Figure 31 shows the CODECO project visible at the ECL booth.

⁴⁴ <https://www.hipeac.net/2025/barcelona/#/program/sessions/8194/>

Figure 29. CODECO presentation at the ML4ECS workshop, collocated with HIPEAC 2025 conference.

Figure 30. Presentation about the CODECO component PDLC, at the ML4ECS workshop.

Figure 31. CODECO presence at the ECL booth at the HIPEAC conference 2025 in Barcelona.

HIPEAC 2026

The HIPEAC 2026 conference⁴⁵ was organised in Krakow, Poland, on January 26th – 28th, 2026. CODECO had a triple presence at this event: at the ECL exhibition booth where it was presented together with sister projects, its own exhibition booth where different CODECO demos were showcased to visitors, and through the presence at the ML4ECS workshop⁴⁶ where CODECO progress and achievements were presented by various partners. The conference attracted around 500 visitors, with researchers, industry representatives, and students among them.

Impact Assessment: The strong presence at the HIPEAC Conference 2026 was part of the CODECO strategy to highlight the transition to Eclipse KuDECO while emphasizing European synergy in the Edge-Cloud continuum. The dedicated session at the ML4ECS workshop facilitated over 20 direct technical inquiries and strengthened the project's position as a leader in cognitive orchestration.

6.3.2.3 AIOTI

AIOTI⁴⁷ focuses on leading, promoting, bridging, and supporting collaboration in IoT and Edge Computing and other converging technologies research and innovation, standardisation, and ecosystem building, providing IoT and Edge Computing deployment for European businesses creating benefits for European society.

Several partners of CODECO, such as FOR, ICOM, and I2CAT, are involved across different Working Groups (WGs) of AIOTI. About the targets of OSS, groups that the consortium believes

45 <https://www.hipeac.net/2026/krakow/#/>

46 <https://www.hipeac.net/2026/krakow/#/program/8241/>

47 <https://aioti.eu/>

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are relevant concern the Horizontal AIOTI groups, *Research and Innovation* and *Standardisation*, and the vertical groups, *Manufacturing, Energy, Mobility*.

The key aspects involving CODECO partners concern the development of a common vision towards IoT-Cloud-Edge, addressing relevant challenges over the next decades (Research and Innovation), and the application of CODECO in its use-cases (Standardisation, specific vertical groups) and other vertical groups.

Impact Assessment: The key aspect under work in AIOTI relates with CODECO awareness and the re-use of CODECO. Currently, the CODECO OSS is being considered across novel project proposals under development with collaboration of AIOTI, and with AIOTI partners.

7 Summary

This deliverable marks the final step of the activities performed under task T7.1 to establish a professional, sustainable, and impactful open-source ecosystem around the project's research results. Over the course of the three-year project, the community-building strategy successfully evolved through three critical stages: from initial awareness (year 1) and technical consolidation (year 2) to the final phase of Sustainability and Exploitation (year 3).

One of the main ambitions in CODECO was to ensure that its research outcomes survive the conclusion of the Horizon Europe funding cycle by delivering "running code" maintained by an active community. The most significant achievement in this regard is the transition of the CODECO Open-Source Toolkit into the formal Eclipse KuDECO project under the Eclipse Foundation. By establishing KuDECO, the project has secured a vendor-neutral governance model, professional infrastructure, and a clear legal framework that facilitates long-term industrial adoption and academic reuse.

Throughout the project, the consortium implemented rigorous open-source best practices, resulting in a high-grade codebase licensed under the business-friendly Apache License 2.0. Continuous IP validation and monitoring of open-source best practices application ensured that the CODECO Toolkit is free from license incompatibilities, making it "business-ready" for commercial exploitation.

Community growth has been robust during the project's lifetime. This was driven by a multi-faceted engagement strategy, including strategic presence at major events, fostering direct dialogue with industrial stakeholders and the research community, the organisation of a Hackathon to engage with the developer community and attracting direct code contributions, or the IRCEP encouraging third-party developers to extend and validate the CODECO framework.

The CODECO Open-Source Toolkit shows the commitment to deliver professional-grade open-source software. With Eclipse KuDECO as a living legacy, the project's innovations in cognitive, decentralized edge-cloud orchestration are now permanently embedded in the European open-source landscape, ready to drive future advancements in the data economy.

Reflecting on the three years of community-building work, several lessons emerge that may be of value to future Horizon Europe projects pursuing similar open-source sustainability goals. Achieving consistent copyright header coverage across a large, multi-partner repository proved more time-consuming than anticipated, particularly for components with significant third-party vendored code; earlier and more frequent automated tooling runs would reduce remediation pressure at the end of the project. Growing a contributor base genuinely beyond the original consortium remains a long-term challenge: while the IRCEP programme and the IETF Hackathon attracted external interest, the majority of the 69 registered developers are consortium members. Eclipse KuDECO's success as a truly independent community will therefore depend on sustained outreach efforts in the post-project period, independent of EU funding cycles. Finally, the dependency on consortium-funded resources for events and challenge awards highlights the importance of securing bridge funding or Eclipse Working Group membership early in the post-project phase, before the current momentum dissipates

8 Appendix 1 – OSS Community-building Year 1

This section summarizes all the community building activities performed during the first twelve months of the CODECO project life, which have been extracted from the previous version of the deliverable D24, with special focus to the ones implemented between M7 and M12, not only because T7.1 had started, but also because the CODECO concept and toolkit had 'taken shape' and were mature enough to be disseminated. open-source perspective.

Similarly to Table 6 in **Section 6**, Table 8 shows the activities (during year Y1), their impact and the contribution to them from the open-source perspective.

Table 8. Open-source community-building activities held until M12.

Dissemination Activity	Targets	Aim	KPIs (D21)	Lead/Contributors	Open-source contributions, year 1	Impact
Media dissemination	All	Dissemination of the overall project development via broad media, e.g., TV, podcasts, YouTube videos, public magazines, and journals.	1 per year	FOR, ECL, INO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website (INO, FOR). - Involvement in EUCEI (open-source, ECL, FOR). - ECL Eclipse2023 CODECO video. - Zenodo community (FOR, INO, UGOE). YouTube (FOR). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website: 250 visitors, over 600 views. - Zenodo: 603 views across all documents; 313 with focus on the deliverables related with OSS. - YouTube: 70 views on the first video since mid-November 2023.
Press releases	All	Dissemination about the overall project development, results, and events	4 per year (multiple partners) reaching to over 500 end-users	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Eclipse newsletter 2023 - FOR online press releases - Social network activities with focus on OSS (INO) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Eclipse newsletter: over 250000 subscribers. - FOR press releases: over 200 views - Social networks: 399 followers in LinkedIn; 91 in Twitter
Industrial Event	DEV, ICT, AR	1 Inception event, industrial workshop (M12) Organised by FOR having as main target industrial stakeholders and aiming at igniting interest in further exploring the use-cases in multiple fields of IoT/Edge.	>50 participants	All	Preparation of demonstrations, code, and presentations/videos for the HiPEAC industrial workshop on 18.01.2023	To be provided after event (18.01.2023); currently 44 attendees from 32 institutions in 14 countries.

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Dissemination Activity	Targets	Aim	KPIs (D21)	Lead/Contributors	Open-source contributions, year 1	Impact
Representation in events	ICT, AR, SDO, EUS	Disseminate CODECO results in different venues, industrial and scientific. Promotion of active participation and discussions on exploitation aspects and community-building.	>50 events	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EclipseCon, Ludwigsburg (Eclipse, dissemination), 16th October 2023 - Eclipse SAAM on Cloud to Edge Continuum (Eclipse, dissemination), 16th October 2023 - 6G CONASENSE workshop (co-located with IEEE WPMC2023, 29th Nov, Orlando, Fl, USA, organized by fortiss) - MobiArch 2023 (UGOE, TID - Workshop Chairs), Madrid, Spain, Oct 6th, 2023. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EclipseCon: over 200 participants. - 6G CONASENSE: 40 participants. - MobiArch 2023: 30 participants.
Advanced training	ICT, AR, DEV, SDO	Transfer results and address potential gaps derived from interaction with the scientific community. Specific events and participation in community events, e.g., summer schools, Webinars, workshops.	>20 organized training events with at least 50 participants	INTRA, ECL	3 trainings provided by ECL: Open-source ecosystem; Open-source licensing and compliance; Open collaboration, open development.	All partners involved, average of 40 persons in each workshop.
CODECO Eclipse GitLab	DEV, ICT, AR	Re-use of OSS code	-	ECL, All	Early release of OSS code as defined in D11, M10	35 followers

In the context of this category of activities, we highlight the Eclipse Newsletter due to its broad outreach. The CODECO project was part of the Eclipse Newsletter in July 2023. The article gave an overview of the CODECO concept and architecture, also about the intended open-source results and already referred to the CODECO GitLab repository. The title was "*CODECO: Supporting the Edge-Cloud Continuum Via an Open, Cognitive, Decentralised Framework*" and can be found on the Eclipse website⁴⁸. Figure 32 shows the first part of the article.

48 <https://newsroom.eclipse.org/eclipse-newsletter/2023/july/codeco-supporting-edge-cloud-continuum-open-cognitive-decentralized>

CODECO: Supporting the Edge-Cloud Continuum Via an Open, Cognitive, Decentralized Framework

Rute C. Sofia Marco Jahn

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The current internet evolution, with an increasing focus on the intertwining of smart, mobile, decentralized IoT services, brings new challenges to the deployment of applications. Applications and their components need to be lightweight, highly portable, and mobile, to run anywhere and everywhere. Secondly, there is a need to handle large amounts of data often with very different features both in terms of computation (processing) and exchange (networking), including those with low latency demands. Third, it is important to guarantee a smooth data flow, to allow for a smooth and secure integration end-to-end, across edge-cloud environments. Fourthly, real-time decision-making on where to compute and to store data must be supported.

CODECO, a Horizon Europe project, is attempting to answer these needs (Figure 1), framing itself as an intelligent and decentralized edge-cloud orchestration framework that addresses the existing infrastructure by considering data, compute, and network resources.

Simplification & Automation	O1: Reduce Edge-Cloud Setup and Management Time
Data-compute-network Orchestration	O2: Optimize Edge-Cloud Operation via a privacy-preserving data-compute-network orchestration
Security & Privacy Preservation	O3: Provide automated, privacy preserving secure management for multi-clusters
Openness & Greenness	O4: Support multi-domain Edge Cloud operations integrating openness and greenness
Broad Impact	O5: Build a consolidated ecosystem appealing to the different CODECO stakeholder groups

Figure 1: The key principles and objectives of CODECO

CODECO develops an ecosystem consisting of open-source toolkits, large-scale experimentation, training tools and events, use-cases across four vertical domains (Smart Cities, Energy, Manufacturing, Smart Buildings) and multiple events integrated into a unique Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme. The open source software, which is pluggable and interoperable with Kubernetes (K8s) will be made available to the community through the Eclipse Foundation.

A Novel Approach to Orchestration: Data-Compute-Network

CODECO will implement software toolkits suitable for smarter management of highly-distributed environments based on heterogeneous networks and by integrating mobile, resource-constrained devices. The CODECO components, illustrated in Figure 2, shall extend the management and orchestration of edge-cloud services with cognitive cross-layer adaptability and with features that allow for intelligent decisions regarding computational offloading and network adaptation while taking into consideration application and networking requirements, data security and sensitivity, as well as other context-specific aspects related to the data flow. CODECO plans to support both single cluster and federated cluster operations.

Figure 32. CODECO article in Eclipse Newsletter in July 2023.

Impact Assessment: The Eclipse Newsletter reaches more than 250.000 subscribers from the wider Eclipse ecosystem. The CODECO article was meant to be the first activity to drop the name “CODECO” and create awareness of the project in the open-source community.

Three other main events were held in 2023, oriented to the DEV, AR, and ICT stakeholder groups:

- **ACM Mobiarch 2023**⁴⁹, having as chairs Tingting Yuan (UGOE) and Luis Contreras Murillo (TID), Madrid, Spain, Oct 6th, 2023. Targets were AR, ICT, and DEV. The workshop counted with a panel session organized by CODECO, dedicated to architectural design, and disseminating the CODECO Eclipse GitLab. It consisted of twenty participants.
- **EclipseCon 2023**, organized by Marco Jahn and David Remon, ECL, in Ludwigsburg, 16th-19th October 2023. CODECO participated in the research projects, with the purpose of community engagement. Targets were DEV, AR, and ICT.

⁴⁹ <https://mobiarch2023.github.io/>

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- **6G CONASENSE 2023⁵⁰**, co-located with IEEE WPMC2023, having as chair Rute C. Sofia (FOR), November 21st, 2023. Targets were AR and ICT. The workshop focused on 6G aspects, and one of the proposed topics was flexible Edge-Cloud continuum. It consisted of fifty participants.

Out of the different events, we highlight EclipseCon 2023 due to the focus and broader reach.

In EclipseCon 2023, CODECO had the opportunity to meet the development community: more than 460 developers, architects, researchers, and managers attended the event. This event lasted a week, starting with a community day on Monday and ending on Thursday after three more days of conference. Figure 33 shows the interaction with the visitors at the booth.

Figure 33. CODECO poster and CODECO team during EclipseCon 2023.

Finally, in addition to the development of specific events and participation in external events, CODECO has been involved in different OSS communities, contributing to the creation of OSS paths in Europe, where the EUCloudEdgeIoT initiative can be highlighted. CODECO engaged in the first EUCloudEdgeIoT concertation meeting⁵¹ both on the project pitching session and having been invited to the panel “Resource orchestration and adaptation in the continuum.” There were around 100 attendees in this session (rf. to Figure 34 for a view on the event).

50 <https://www.conasense.org/conasense-2023/>

51 <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/concentration-and-consultation-meeting-on-computing-continuum-uniting-the-european-ict-community-for-a-digital-future/>

Figure 34. First EUCloudEdgeIoT concertation meeting, May 10th-11th 2023, Brussels.

9 Appendix 2 – OSS Community-building Year 2

Table 9 summarises the main activities performed in CODECO during the project's first two years, under the "community-building" umbrella, with special focus to the ones implemented between M12 and M24, as the activities during M1-M12 had already been duly reported in the previous deliverables D24 and D25, and are available in the previous annex.

Typically, open-source community activities contribute to a range of communication and dissemination categories and related KPIs as explained in the CODECO Deliverable *D21 – Dissemination, Communication, Promotion Plan* [7]. The next table shows, among the dissemination activities for the CODECO project, their measures of impact listed in that Deliverable, the specific KPIs regarding open-source and the contribution to them from the open-source perspective.

Table 9. Open-source community-building activities held until M24.

Activity	Targets	Aim	KPIs (D21)	Lead/Contributors	Contributions	Impact
Media dissemination	All	Dissemination of the overall project development via broad media, e.g., TV, podcasts, YouTube videos, public magazines, and journals.	1 per year	FOR, ECL, INO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website (INO, FOR). - Involvement in EUCEI (open-source, ECL, FOR). - EclipseCon2023 CODECO video (ECL). - Zenodo community⁵² (FOR, INO, UGOE). - YouTube (FOR)⁵³. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website: 5295 views corresponding to 3256 visitors. - Zenodo: 3372 views and 2835 downloads across all documents; 817 views and 735 downloads with focus on the deliverables related with OSS. - YouTube: 104 total views in the CODECO exclusive channel.
Press releases	All	Dissemination about the overall project development, results, and events.	4 per year (multiple partners) reaching to over 500 end-users.	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Eclipse newsletter 2023. - FOR online press releases. - Social network activities with focus on OSS. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Eclipse newsletter: over 250000 subscribers. - FOR press releases: over 200 views. - Social networks: 536 followers in LinkedIn; 134 in X (former Twitter).
Industrial Event	DEV, ICT, AR	1 Inception event, industrial workshop (M12) Organised by FOR having as main target industrial stakeholders and aiming at	>50 participants	All	Preparation of demonstrations, code, and presentations/videos for the HiPEAC industrial workshop on 18.01.2023.	1 st Industrial Workshop: 62 attendees including students, researchers and SMEs.

⁵² <https://zenodo.org/communities/he-codeco>

⁵³ First video added in M11 (November 2023).

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Activity	Targets	Aim	KPIs (D21)	Lead/Contributors	Contributions	Impact
		igniting interest in further exploring the use-cases in multiple fields of IoT/Edge.				
Representation in events	ICT, AR, SDO, EUS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disseminate CODECO results in different venues, industrial and scientific. - Promotion of active participation and discussions on exploitation aspects and community-building. 	>50 events	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EclipseCon (ECL), Ludwigsburg, Germany, 16th October 2023. - Eclipse SAAM on Cloud to Edge Continuum (ECL), 16th October 2023. - 6G CONASENSE workshop (FOR), co-located with IEEE WPMC2023, Orlando, USA, 29th Nov 2023. - MobiArch 2023 (UGOE, TID), Madrid, Spain, Oct 6th, 2023. - EUCEI concertation meeting (FOR), Brussels, Belgium, 10th to 11th May 2023. - WF-IoT 2023 (FOR), Aveiro, Portugal, 23rd October 2023. - Nexus Forum 2023 (i2CAT), Brussels, Belgium, 5th to 6th October 2023. - AI-SPRINT final event (FOR), online, 11th October 2023. - Embedded World 2024 (ECL), Nuremberg, Germany, 9th to 11th April 2024. - Dev.Conf.CZ (RHT), Brno, Czechia, 13th to 15th June 2024. - AAAI2023 (UGOE), Washington DC, USA, 14th to 15th February 2023, - EUCNC CONASENSE 2024 (FOR), Antwerpen, Belgium, 3rd June 2024. - IEEE ISCC ECO 2024 (ATH), Paris, France, 26th June 2024, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -EclipseCon: over 200participants. - 6G CONASENSE: 40 participants. - MobiArch 2023: 30 participants. - EUCEI Concertation meeting: >100 participants. - WF-IoT 2023: 70 participants. - Nexus Forum 2023: >100 participants. - AI-SPRINT final event: 70 participants. - Embedded World 2024 : >100 participants. - DevConf.CZ : >100 participants. - AAAI2023 : >20 participants. - EUCNC CONASENSE 2024 : 60 participants. - IEEE ISCC ECO 2024: 20 participants.
Advanced training ⁵⁴	ICT, AR,	- Transfer results and address potential gaps	>20 organized training events	INTRA, ECL	3 trainings provided by ECL: Open-source ecosystem; Open-source licensing and compliance; Open	All partners involved, average of 40 persons in each workshop.

54 Advanced training activities in CODECO are to be started in year 3 of the project, T7.4. However, partner Eclipse has started advanced training internally for the consortium, to bootstrap an understanding of building results towards OSS.

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Activity	Targets	Aim	KPIs (D21)	Lead/Contributors	Contributions	Impact
	DEV, SDO	derived from interaction with the scientific community. - Specific events and participation in community events, e.g., summer schools, Webinars, workshops.	with at least 50 participants		collaboration, open development.	
CODECO GitLab Repository	DEV, ICT, AR	Re-use of OSS code. Community engagement.	N/A	ECL, All	- Early release of OSS code as defined in D11, M10. CODECO Open-source Toolkit, and in D12. - Continuous development, open and transparent collaboration.	52 developers

Having in mind the focus of OSS community-building, several efforts were done, as described in Table 6:

- Across the CODECO LinkedIn space, partner INO has been driving several dissemination activities, covering OSS results of the project, such as software release, among others. The CODECO LinkedIn has a total of 1706 page views with 536-page visitors.
- The Website has reached 3256 visitors, corresponding to a total of 5295 views.
- The CODECO Zenodo community has reached a total of 3372 views and 2835 downloads, where 817 views and 735 downloads correspond to deliverables associated with the CODECO OSS components and architecture (deliverables D8, D9, D10, D11, D12).
- Different press releases have reached over two hundred views.
- CODECO's exclusive YouTube Channel, with 12 videos having been uploaded to it, totaling 104 views and 6 subscribers.

In terms of events, some key events were held during the second year of project life, 2024, oriented to the DEV, AR, and ICT stakeholder groups:

- **OCX 2024**, organized by ECL, in Mainz, Germany, 22nd – 24th October 2024. Targets were DEV, AR, and ICT. It replaces the previous EclipseCon. CODECO participated on the *Research@Eclipse* booth, with the purpose of community engagement.
- **EUCNC CONASENSE 2024**⁵⁵, organized by EUCNC in Antwerp, Belgium, 3rd June 2024. Targets were AR and ICT. The workshop focused on the continuous alignment of CODECO as a representative of 6G Cloud-Edge-IOT architecture and interaction with other EU projects.
- **Embedded World 2024**⁵⁶, organized by ECL, in Nuremberg, Germany, 9th - 11th April 2024, depicted in Figure 35. Targets were DEV and ICT. With more than 32,000 attendees at the event, CODECO was present at a booth and had the opportunity to do networking with other stakeholders.
- **DevConf2024**, organized by RHT, in Brno, Czech Republic, 13th – 15th June 2024. Targets were DEV, AR, and ICT. Dean Kelly and Alka Nixon had the opportunity to give a talk: *Introduction of CODECO, overview, architecture, Red Hat work on CODECO*. More than

⁵⁵ <https://www.eucnc.eu/programme/workshops/workshop-11/>

⁵⁶ <https://www.embedded-world.de/en>

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1,100 attendees registered at the event, making it an opportunity to meet the developer community.

- **European Big Data Value Forum 2024⁵⁷**, organized by BDVA, in Budapest, Hungary, 2nd – 4th October. Targets were AR, GOV, and ICT. The event focused on advanced policy actions and industrial and research activities in the areas of Data and AI. CODECO was represented in one of the sessions, titled "*AI and data over computing continuum*", where the latest developments in the projects were highlighted.
- **AIOTI Days 2024⁵⁸**, organized by the Alliance for IoT and Edge Computing Innovation (AIOTI), in Brussels, Belgium, 24th – 26th September 2024. Targets were DEV, AR, and ICT. Rute C. Sofia presented CODECO's architecture and its experimental framework. The workshop focused on the exploration of how the continuum and digital twins meet virtual worlds in industrial space, creating a physical-digital virtual continuum.
- **Red Hat Tech Talk**, organized by RHT, in Cork, Ireland, 14th February 2024. Targets were DEV, AR, and ICT. Dean Kelly and Alka Nixon had a talk in front of 60 attendees: *Introduction to CODECO, overview*. Figure 36 shows a capture of the talk.

Figure 35. CODECO at Embedded World 2024, in Nuremberg.

⁵⁷ <https://european-big-data-value-forum.eu/>

⁵⁸ <https://aioti.eu/aioti-days-2024/>

Figure 36. Red Hat team presenting CODECO at Tech talk, Ireland.

Figure 37: CODECO present at OCX 2024.

Out of the different events, we highlight OCX 2024 due to the focus and broader reach.

In OCX 2024, CODECO attended the Open Community Experience (OCX). The event lasted 4 days, with a variety of collocated events addressing innovative CODECO-related topics, such as embedded IoT and edge, automotive and mobility and supply chain security, among others.

Impact Assessment: OCX, formerly EclipseCon, is the Eclipse Foundation’s flagship conference and meeting point for developers, architects, researchers and open-source business leaders to learn about Eclipse technologies, share experiences and best practices in open-source software development, and more. More than 430 attendees had the opportunity to gain experience about CODECO at the Research Booth, shown in

the CODECO poster displayed at the poster session, and the flyers and stickers produced and distributed, resulting in good acceptance among the developer community.

In addition to the development of specific events, and participation in external events, CODECO has been involved in different OSS communities, contributing to the creation of OSS paths in Europe. The contributions to three of these initiatives can be highlighted: EUCloudEdgeIoT, HiPEAC and AIOTI.

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EUCloudEdgeIoT Engagement

The EUCloudEdgeIoT.eu initiative aims to realise a pathway for the understanding and development of the Cloud, Edge and IoT continuum by promoting cooperation between a wide range of research projects, developers and suppliers, business users and potential adopters of this new technological paradigm. The initiative manages six Task Forces (TFs): TF1 Strategic Liaisons, TF2 Open-source Engagement, TF3 Architecture, TF4 Ecosystem Engagement, TF5 Market and Sectors, TF6 Communications.

Different partners in CODECO are engaging across all TFs. Specifically, FOR is involved in TF1, TF3, and TF6. ECL leads TF2, therefore providing input from CODECO as well. ATOS leads TF3. Moreover, INO is expected to engage in TF1, TF4, and TF6 in the context of the CODECO Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme (IRCEP), which started in 2024. Key contributions of CODECO in the context of EUCloudEdgeIoT are expected to result from its framework (architecture and taxonomy); OSS guidelines (TF2); use-case aspects towards SDOs (TF1).

Impact Assessment: For CODECO, the EUCloudEdgeIoT.eu initiative is an excellent opportunity to interact and align with the cluster of similar European projects and share ongoing work and results within relevant working groups. What is also relevant is the definition of taxonomy and the architectural view for the Edge-Cloud continuum where CODECO is involved. For the period being reported, in addition to contributions to TF3 (taxonomy, architecture), CODECO has engaged in TF1 in the context of developed white papers, and concerning its use-cases, and novelty concerning Edge/IoT applications.

HiPEAC

The HiPEAC initiative addresses topics across the compute continuum from Edge to Cloud, HiPEAC is a network of around 2,000 world-class computing systems researchers, industry representatives, and students, i.e. the AR, ICT and DEV stakeholder of CODECO. CODECO organised an industrial workshop in HiPEAC 2024, has prepared another workshop for the HiPEAC 2025 Conference⁵⁹ and is going to regularly engage with the initiative across different activities, e.g., summer schools via the CODECO IRCEP programme (T7.2, started in April 2024, M16 of CODECO).

CODECO had a first contact with the HiPEAC community at the project's first industrial workshop⁶⁰, inception event, which took place on 18.01.2024, co-located with HiPEAC 2024, in Munich. The HiPEAC conference run over three days and attracted over 1000 participants. The event targeted AR, ICT, and the DEV community as well. It provided demonstrations based on the CODECO Toolkit open-source code; presentations and videos about the CODECO use-cases were shown. It also counted with a panel involving two other projects of the cognitive continuum, COGNIFOG⁶¹, and COGNIT⁶².

The second HiPEAC community initiative will take place on January 22nd, 2025, with a Machine Learning for Edge-Cloud Systems⁶³ (ML4ECS) workshop where CODECO will have a dedicated session.

Impact Assessment: The first event attracted over 20 attendees, among the 44 registered participants. The aim was to ignite interest across HiPEAC, which will be continued with other related activities, targeting the community, such as the workshop at HiPEAC 2025, participation in summer schools, etc.

59 <https://www.hipeac.net/2025/barcelona/#/>

60 <https://he-codeco.eu/codeco-industrial-workshop/>

61 <https://cognifog.eu/>

62 <https://cognit.sovereignedge.eu/>

63 <https://www.hipeac.net/2025/barcelona/#/program/sessions/8194/>

Figure 38. First CODECO inception workshop, collocated with HIPEAC 2024 conference.

AIOTI

AIOTI⁶⁴ focuses on leading, promoting, bridging, and supporting collaboration in IoT and Edge Computing and other converging technologies research and innovation, standardisation, and ecosystem building, providing IoT and Edge Computing deployment for European businesses creating benefits for European society. Several partners of CODECO, such as FOR, ICOM, and I2CAT, are involved across different Working Groups (WGs) of AIOTI. Regarding the targets of OSS, groups that the consortium believes are relevant concern the Horizontal AIOTI groups, *Research and Innovation* and *Standardisation*, and the vertical groups, *Manufacturing*, *Energy*, *Mobility*.

The key aspects involving CODECO partners concern the development of a common vision towards IoT-Cloud-Edge, addressing relevant challenges over the next decades (Research and Innovation), and the application of CODECO in its use-cases (Standardisation, specific vertical groups) and other vertical groups.

Impact Assessment: The key aspect under work in AIOTI relates with CODECO awareness and the re-use of CODECO. Currently, the CODECO OSS is being considered across novel project proposals under development with collaboration of AIOTI, and with AIOTI partners.

⁶⁴ <https://aioti.eu/>

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